

Role of Herbal Medicines in Cancer of Pharmacokinetic and Pharmacodynamic Properties: A Comprehensive Overview

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ABSTRACT

Herbal Medicines are used popularly in a wide variety of ailments like, diabetes, heart diseases and cancer due to fewer side effects. According to World Health Organization (WHO), cancer is a leading cause of death worldwide, accounting for nearly 10 million deaths in 2020 and in 2024, 2,001,140 new cancer cases and 611,720 cancer deaths are projected to occur in the United States (US) itself. The cost of new drugs entering the market, especially of cancer treatment is costing around \$100,000 per patient in a treatment year. However, natural medicines are cost-effective and can be useful in addition to the conventional chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and immunotherapy. The mechanism of action of the natural medicines are well established and they act via cannabinoid receptor 1 (CB1), Transient Receptor Potential Vanilloid 1 (TRPV1), and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-gamma (PPAR γ), PI3K-AKT pathways. In contrast, they act via altering different pharmacokinetic pathways i.e., absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME). Considering the above, this review delineates the value and ways of herbal or natural medicines in cancer by modernising our understanding.

Keywords: Herbal Medicines, Cancer, Apoptosis, ADME, P-gp, BRCP.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT: Mechanism of Herbals in Cancer prevention

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INTRODUCTION

Herbal medications, widely used worldwide, are important in chronic illness management and health promotion. Over 11,000 plant species are used medicinally, with approximately 200 being the most often used. About 80% of individuals in many poor countries and one-third of adults in affluent nations use herbal treatments for a variety of health issues, ranging from cold to chronic disorders like diabetes, heart diseases and cancer [Wang HP et al., 2018]. Plants provide an important compound for the treatment of diseases and serve as an inspiration for drug research. Of all novel medications developed between 1983 and 1994, 41% were from natural sources, 60% of which contained anti-infective and anticancer properties. Concentrated, unmodified extracts were used in the early usage of herbs. Herbal activities are complex because they are the product of compound mixtures rather than individual ingredients [Efferth T et al., 2007]. Chinese medicine, which has a 2000-year heritage, promotes the use of herbs and medications in combination for greater therapeutic advantages over modern medicine. Recent research shows that herb-drug combinations can combat chemoresistance, prompting interest in cancer therapy [Yagüe E et al., 2022]. The popularity of medicinal plants rises due their accessibility and fewer side effects. Herbal remedies are a useful adjunct to other medical interventions, such as the management of type 2 diabetes (T2DM) and cardiovascular diseases. Combining traditional Chinese medicine with modern cancer treatment increases the effectiveness of the treatment, lowers side effects, and improves patient satisfaction [Salmerón-Manzano E et al., 2020].

Herbal remedies are inexpensive, low-toxic, and produce useful substances like, vinca alkaloids and paclitaxel, which are frequently found by accident or after thorough screening. With an emphasis on the preventive and protective activities of natural substances through cellular defence mechanisms, current cancer research focuses on medications and vaccines targeting critical molecules to suppress tumour growth, metastasis, and proliferation [Li L et al., 2014]. Plants high in flavonoids provide a variety of health advantages, such as antiviral, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer effects; nevertheless, there is conflicting data about their

ability to prevent colorectal neoplasms. Cancer prevention evidence is lacking for *Panax ginseng*'s immunological and antihyperglycemic reputation. Onions, or *Allium cepa*, and *Aegle marmelos* are thought to have antioxidant and anticancer properties, while aloe vera strengthens the immune system's defences against cancer [Manandhar B et al., 2018]. Research is being done on broccoli (*Brassica leracea*) as a chemo-preventive agent, while *ginkgo biloba* is thought to be an antioxidant. The collective action of phytochemicals found in entire fruits and vegetables highlights their potential to lower cancer risk potential. Herbal medicine is becoming more popular as a cancer preventive strategy amid worries about conventional treatments [Yu J et al., 2024].

Natural chemicals can be categorized based on their molecular structure, intended use, or signalling pathways. Natural substances can be categorized in the following ways based on their chemical structure: carotenoids (lycopene, alpha and beta carotene), tannins, coumarins, alkaloids, nitrogen compounds, phenolic compounds (phenolic acids, flavonoids, stilbenes (resveratrol), isothiocyanates, and indoles, and organosulphates (for instance; garlic). The subclassification of flavonoids includes chalcones (epigallocatechin), flavanones (naringenin), flavones (apigenin, luteolin), flavonols (quercetin, kaempferol), isoflavones (genistein), and anthocyanins. In certain instances, complete plant extracts containing a complex of natural chemicals showed action in *in-vitro* or *in-vivo* experiments. Cannabinoids from *Cannabis sativa* is used in Chinese medicine, which has a long history of using cannabis in pain management. The plant has more than 60 cannabinoids, terpenoids, and flavonoids. Most of the studies point the possibility of cannabis in anti-cancer therapy, notwithstanding their prevalent usage in palliative chemotherapy. Cannabinoids have been shown *in-vitro* and animal studies to induce apoptosis, inhibit proliferation and angiogenesis, and prevent metastasis in a vast majority of cancers. D9-tetrahydrocannabinol (D9-THC) is one of the main bioactive compounds that has been shown to have anti-tumour effects in number of cancers, including skin, breast, prostate, lung, and glioma [McCulloch M et al., 2006].

Drug interactions, which are frequently caused by modifications in transporters and metabolizing enzymes, affect the absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) of various medications. Absorption is impacted by changes in intestinal uptake and efflux transporters, and plasma and tissue exposure are impacted by changes in metabolism and excretion caused by hepatic/renal transporters and enzymes [Xiang Y et al., 2019].

2. Herbs against Cancer

A key component of the human diet are plant polyphenols, such as curcumin, which is obtained from *Curcuma spp.* and has a variety of pharmacological advantages, such as anti-aging, anti-cancer, and anti-inflammatory effects. Studies reveals that curcumin inhibits the development of cancer cells by causing apoptosis, stopping their multiplication, damaging their DNA, and causing a cell to stop to their growth. The process influences the p53 protein and initiates intracellular signals through the generation of reactive oxygen species and cytochrome C. Since curcumin counteracts DNA damage induced by oxidative causes such as ionizing radiation, it has been shown in several cellular and preclinical investigations to have an inhibitory function in the formation of cancer. This is partly due to its capacity to trap free radicals [Yeh M et al., 2020].

Traditional Chinese tonic *astragalus* supports the adrenal glands, lungs, and digestive system, promoting metabolism and decreasing fatigue. Its strong immunomodulatory effects, which boost the generation of interferon- γ (IFN- γ), tumour necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), and stimulate immune cells, have been documented in recent research. The *spp. Astragalus* has many health benefits, including anti-viral, blood glucose regulating, lipid-lowering, anti-fibrosis, antibacterial, and anti-radiation qualities. It also has anti-aging and anti-tumour actions. In addition to chemotherapy, Chinese herbal medicines (CHMs), particularly *Astragalus*, have the potential to reduce toxicity and increase effectiveness in advanced non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC). According to research clinical trials, *astragalus* boosts immunity and, in randomized trials, it may improve tumour response, survival, performance status, and decrease chemotherapy toxicity when used with

platinum-based chemotherapy [McCulloch M, et al., 2006].

The CHMs suppress cancers, boost natural killer cells (NK cells), and decrease adverse effects of treatment. While cellular and animal investigations concentrate on specific herbs such as *Ganoderma lucidum* and *Angelica sinensis*, clinical trials tend to favour CHM mixtures [Sohretoglu D et al., 2018]. A traditional medicinal mushroom called *Cordyceps militaris* has shown potential in the treatment of cancer. By blocking human telomerase reverse transcriptase (hTERT) transcriptional activity, its water extract causes A549 cells to undergo apoptosis via death receptor and mitochondria-mediated pathways, which in turn reduces telomerase activity [Shweta et al., 2023]. According to Bahmani et al., *Centaurea albonitens* extract increases vincristine's cytotoxicity against leukaemia cells without affecting normal cells [Bahmani F et al., 2018].

Plant extracts with doxorubicin, such as *Solanum nigrum Linn.*, enhance anticancer effects by activating autophagy. By modulating pro-inflammatory cytokines, *Agrocybe aegerita* polysaccharides and *S. nigrum Linn.* extract boost 5-fluorouracil's (5-FU) cytotoxicity against various malignancies [Lin S et al., 2020]. In breast cancer cells, phenolic acids (caffeic, rosmarinic, and ursolic) increase paclitaxel's cytotoxicity. Studies show that natural chemicals, particularly flavonoids and phenolics, have the potential to synergize with recognized anticancer drugs to improve their efficacy. Curcumin, a well-studied natural substance, improves chemotherapy efficacy in common malignancies via modulating nuclear factor- $\kappa\beta$ (NF- $\kappa\beta$). Herbal medicine enhancers that target oxidative stress and NF- β have the potential to help chemotherapy to work against cancer cells [Bracci L et al., 2014].

Quercetin, an antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory flavonoid, inhibits cell proliferation, promotes apoptosis, and initiates cell cycle arrest. It synergizes with triazofurin in ovarian cancer, increasing efficacy while decreasing negative effects. Green tea's Epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) catechins reduce cancer risk and boost chemopreventive activity when coupled with sulindac and tamoxifen. Thearubigins in black tea, when coupled with genistein, inhibit

prostate cancer cell proliferation. Green tea components improve doxorubicin transport to cancer cells while protecting the heart from cardiotoxicity, implying a role in cancer therapy [Efferth T et al., 2007]. Curcumin, a phenolic acid derivative of turmeric, has been intensively researched for its chemopreventive properties. It has powerful anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anti-cancer activities that affect various pathways. Curcumin inhibits colon cancer cell invasion, decreases inflammatory markers, inhibits cell proliferation, promotes apoptosis, and inhibits metastasis, implying great therapeutic promise in various malignancies [Amalraj A et al., 2017]. Resveratrol, a stilbene present in many plants, slows cell proliferation, and has anti-cancer properties. It binds to cytochrome P450 (CYP-450), inhibits inflammation mediator enzymes, and decreases NF- κ B activity. *Ganoderma lucidum* (GLC) has anti-tumour and immunotherapeutic effects, increasing NK cell cytotoxicity and suppressing metastasis-related transcription factors. GLC triterpenoids, especially ganoderic acids, decrease tumour growth by suppressing cell proliferation, inducing apoptosis, and inhibiting tumour growth, indicating their potential for cancer treatment [Huang X et al., 2019].

Several phenolic substances, including curcumin, ginger, and resveratrol, have been shown to have cytotoxic effects on cancers via apoptosis. Curcumin prevents carcinogenesis in colorectal, pancreatic, gastric, and prostate cancers, works as a chemosensitizer, and increases the effects of doxorubicin. The alkaloid 7-hydroxystaurosporine (UCN-01) increases the cytotoxicity of cisplatin, and the Korean mistletoe lectin-C (KML-C) from Korean mistletoe has cytotoxic and apoptotic effects on malignancies. The terpenoid xanthorrhizol prevents tumour growth and metastasis [Safarzadeh E et al., 2014].

3. Herbal medicines: Challenges as monotherapy against cancer

a) Herbal Compounds as Substrates of Various Drug Transporters:

Drug absorption is limited by P-glycoprotein (P-gp)/multidrug resistant 1 (MDR1)/ATP-binding cassette sub-family B member 1 (ABCB1), which is expressed in the intestine. MRP2/ABCC2,

MRP4/ABCC4, and breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP)/ATP binding cassette sub-family G member 1 (ABCG1) act as obstacles to various medicines absorption. Herbal substances identified as P-gp substrates may influence the absorption and bioavailability of herbal treatments. Some herbs also interact with other drug transporters, such as BCRP/ABCG1 and multidrug resistance proteins (MRPs)/ABCs [Juvale A et al., 2022].

b) Hepatic Metabolism of Herbal Medicines in Humans

Cytochrome P450s (CYP-450), flavin-containing monooxygenases, and other enzymes catalyze oxidative or reductive phase I processes in the human hepatic metabolism of herbal medicines. Following phase II processes, such as sulfation and glucuronidation, increase excretion. Co-administered pharmaceuticals or herbal medicines that modify these enzymes may affect the disposition, clearance of herbal medications and thus may cause toxicity [Zhao M et al., 2021].

c) CYP-Mediated Metabolism

The human CYP superfamily, which consists of 58 pseudogenes and 57 functional genes, is important in both endogenous and external chemical metabolism. Over 90% of clinical medicines are oxidatively metabolized by members of the CYP1, CYP2, and CYP3 families, while other families (CYPs 4, 7, 11, 17, 19, and 21) metabolize endogenous compounds. CYP1, 2, and 3 members frequently metabolize herbal therapeutic substances [Zhao M et al., 2021].

d) Uridine 5'-diphospho-glucuronosyltransferase (UGT) Mediated Conjugation

The UGT1A1, 1A8, and 1A9 are essential for the conjugation of flavonoids, anthraquinones, coumarins, tea catechins, and curcuminoids, among other herbal chemicals. They support the glucuronidation of galanin, genistein, daidzein, resveratrol, eupatilin, and curcuminoids as well as the breakdown of soybean isoflavones, demonstrating the varied roles that UGT enzymes play in the metabolism of herbal compounds [Jarrar Y et al., 2021].

e) Sulfotransferases(SULT)-Mediated Conjugation

Members of the cytosolic SULT superfamily are important in the sulfonation of a wide range of chemicals, including xenobiotics, medicines, herbal drugs, dangerous compounds, and others. In "Sho-saiko-to" consumers, the SULT1A subfamily, which is notably responsible for sulfating phenolic-type compounds, facilitates the sulfonation of xenobiotics and herbs, such as baicalin's metabolite baicalein 6-O-sulfate [Bai J et al., 2022].

f) Intestinal Metabolism of Herbal Medicines in Humans

Herbal compounds are significantly metabolized in the human gut by CYP and UGT family, which affects their bioavailability and oral absorption. A vital barrier that affects absorption is intestinal CYP3A4, and the gut's hydrolysis process releases active metabolites. Components of ginseng are transformed by intestinal microorganisms, and tannins are hydrolyzed. When licorice is digested, glycyrrhetic acid is produced, which inhibits 11-BOHD-2 and can cause electrolyte imbalances and possibly health problems if exposure is sustained [Yu YK et al., 2020].

g) Distribution of Herbal Medicines in Humans

Plasma proteins such as globulin, lipoprotein, α -acid glycoprotein (AGP), and human serum albumin (HSA) interact reversibly, impacting medication ADME and pharmacodynamics. Drug distribution, free fraction determination, and drug toxicity are all affected by these interactions. HSA, a key plasma protein, binds to a variety of drugs, affecting their pharmacological effects. The hydrophobic cavities of the HSA improve solubility and control drug delivery and disposal. Berberine-HSA interactions were discovered to be electrostatic, with berberine binding to the hydrophobic pocket. The blood-brain barrier, which is made up of ABC transporters and tight junctions, prevents herbal compounds from entering the brain and so affecting central nervous system efficacy. The involvement of hepatic transporters in herbal remedy biliary excretion is unknown [Zhang W et al., 2011].

h) Elimination of Herbal Medicines in Humans

Herbal medicine preparations are absorbed, metabolized, and then excreted by the kidneys or faeces after being taken orally. Plant natural products leave quantifiable metabolites or parent components in urine and faeces because of their quick elimination half-life. The main method of eliminating herbal components is urine excretion, with biliary excretion and drug transporters playing a small role. As a conjugated metabolite, quercetin has a 7.4% urine excretion rate, although wogonin and baicalein have different renal excretion patterns. Similar to quercetin, biliary excretion, facilitated by MRPs and ABC transporters, is a typical pathway for the clearance of herbal therapeutic substances [Xu X et al., 2020].

i) Problem With Herbal Drug Development

Herbal medication development is complicated by the large number of plant species, of which only a small fraction has been studied for therapeutic purposes. Only a few herbal compounds are listed in Japanese pharmacopeia and Ayurvedic pharmacopoeias. Environmental factors influences and growth patterns affect medicinal value. The natural harvesting of 90% of Indian medicinal herbs depletes available supplies. Environmental changes have an impact on photosynthesis, cultivation techniques, pollution, and the development of plants, changing their medicinal qualities [Gowthami R et al., 2021].

4. Other Applications

4.1 Herbal drugs as cytotoxic agents:

Herbal medications, which are derived from plants, have attracted a lot of attention because of their potential as cytotoxic agents in cancer treatment. These chemicals display cytotoxicity by interfering with numerous cellular processes, making them promising anti-cancer treatment options. Paclitaxel, a drug produced from the Pacific yew tree, affects microtubule dynamics, causing cell cycle arrest and apoptosis [Liu Y et al., 2023].

Similarly, by interfering with the development of microtubules by vincristine, and vinblastine, which are derived from the Madagascar periwinkle, are cytotoxic in nature. These herbal remedies have been used to treat ovarian and breast cancer, among other cancers. Vinorelbine is one of the chemicals from the *Vinca rosea* plant that has cytotoxic qualities; it disrupts microtubule assembly and inhibits mitosis, which is beneficial for treating lung and breast malignancies [Banyal A et al., 2023]. Camptothecin from the Chinese Happy Tree is another intriguing herbal cytotoxic agent. Camptothecin prevents Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) replication and unwinding by blocking DNA topoisomerase I, causing cancer cells to die. In therapeutic settings, its derivatives, topotecan and irinotecan, are used to treat lung, colorectal, and ovarian cancers [Martino E et al., 2017]. Furthermore, artemisinin of *Artemisia annua* has been shown to have cytotoxic effects on cancer cells. Although artemisinin and its derivatives were initially discovered for their anti-malarial properties, they also show promise for anticancer effects via a variety of routes, including the induction of apoptosis and the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [Septembre-Malaterre A et al., 2020]. Anthracyclines, especially anthracyclines such as doxorubicin, daunorubicin, epirubicin, and idarubicin, are vital in the treatment of cancer. Anthracyclines produce cytotoxicity, blocking topoisomerase II and interfering with DNA and ribonucleic acid (RNA). Although anthracycline therapy is helpful in shrinking tumors, there are known for their cardiotoxicity. Bleomycin is another powerful anticancer antibiotic that attaches to metal ions; in order to break down DNA. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (USFDA) has approved it to treat a range of malignancies because of its unique mechanism and efficacy [Mattioli R et al., 2023].

Ganoderma lucidum, often known as the Reishi mushroom, contains about 200 pharmacologically active triterpenoids, including ganoderic acids, which inhibit farnesyl protein transferases (FTase), which are required for the activation of the Ras oncoprotein, which is involved in cell transformation. Glucose transporters (GLT) from Reishi inhibits colon tumour development and proliferation in HT-29 colon cancer cells via apoptosis and G0/G1 phase cell cycle arrest. GLT induces autophagy by inhibiting p38 mitogen-

activated protein kinase (MAPK), as established in cell lines and xenograft models [Sohretoglu D et al., 2018]. The research investigates the possible therapeutic effects of aidi injection (ADI) in lung cancer by altering critical pathways such as thyroid hormone signalling, MAPK, and Phosphatidylinositol-3-kinase (PI3K-Akt). The findings support clinical use and provide references for further study into the pharmacological mechanisms of ADI in the treatment of lung cancer [Lu Y et al., 2022].

Chinese medicine has traditionally used *Cannabis sativa's* ability to reduce pain and induce hallucinations. Cannabinoids, which contain more than 60 different cannabinoids, such as D9-tetrahydrocannabinol (D9-THC), are used in palliative chemotherapy and have potential use in anti-cancer therapy. Studies show that D9-THC has anticancer effects on a variety of malignancies and suppresses the growth of tumors. Rich in *Cannabis sativa*, cannabidiol (CBD) has antiproliferative properties without causing damage to healthy cells. CBD slows the growth of tumors and pre-neoplastic lesions *in-vivo*. CBD exhibits chemopreventive effects through cannabinoid receptor 1 (CB1), Transient Receptor Potential Vanilloid 1 (TRPV1), and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-gamma (PPAR γ) when administered with Sativex (Nabiximol) for multiple sclerosis, highlighting its promise in cancer therapy and preventive care [Brown JD et al., 2021].

Herbal medicines have a wide range of applications and can be used to treat cancer in several ways by concentrating on certain cellular processes that are necessary for cancer cells to survive. However, further study is required to fully understand the mechanisms of herbal medicines, determine the best dosages, and handle any possible side effects before incorporating them into conventional cancer therapies.

4.2 Synergistic Agents

Panax ginseng and 5-FU both inhibit the human gastric cancer cell line BGC823. This effect is mediated by the generation of nitric oxide (NO), which directly affects BGC823 cell development by causing G0/G1 phase arrest *via* the Akt signalling

pathway. Ginsenosides stimulate NO generation by activating endothelial NO synthase (eNOS) through the ER-mediated PI3-kinase/Akt pathway [Ni B et al., 2022].

Also, the ginseng active components show, that transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β) is a transformational molecule that is essential for cell differentiation, tissue repair, and immunosuppression. TGF- β signalling activates the Smad 2/3 molecule, which stimulates endothelial cell proliferation. GRh4 has powerful anti-gastric cancer capabilities *in-vivo* and *in-vitro*, drastically lowering the proliferation and colony formation of GC cells HGC-27 and BGC-823 via the six1-dependent TGF-/Smad2/3 signalling pathway. Ginseng's immune-boosting properties may help chemotherapy. TNF- α , interleukin-1 (IL-1), interleukin-6 (IL-6), stem cell factor (SCF), and granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF, also called CSF-2) are among the cytokines that are increased by Korean ginseng. Polysaccharides promote lymphocyte proliferation, NK cell cytotoxicity, and macrophage activity while increasing spleen weight and serum TNF-, IL-12, IFN- γ , and C-reactive protein (CRP) levels. More research is needed to be discovered to understand ginseng actually improves chemotherapy outcomes. The potent component of *Panax ginseng*, called ginsenosides, can make doxorubicin more sensitive to colorectal cancer cells [Ratan ZA et al., 2021].

According to Bahmani et al., the extract of *Centaurea albonitens* improves vincristine's cytotoxicity against leukaemia cells while preserving its cytotoxicity against normal cells. Combining plant extracts decreases doxorubicin cardiotoxicity and resistance; extract from *Solanum nigrum* Linn. promotes autophagy and improves doxorubicin anti-tumour efficacy. Polysaccharides extracted from *Agrocybe aegerita* and *S. nigrum* Linn. improve the cytotoxicity of 5-fluorouracil against colorectal, ovarian, and esophageal cancers. Paclitaxel's cytotoxicity in *ex vivo* breast cancer cells is increased when mixed with natural phenolic acids (caffeic, rosmarinic, and ursolic acid), revealing the ability of natural substances to improve on well-known anticancer drugs [Bahmani F et al., 2018]. For colon cancer treatment, Chinese herbal medicines such as irinotecan (CPT-11) and Kang'ai (KA) injections are

frequently used with chemotherapy. During pharmacokinetic interactions in rats, it was discovered that pre-mixed co-administration dramatically boosted CPT-11 plasma levels while exposing fewer tissues than segregated co-administration. Through extensive preclinical and clinical research, scientific foundations for these combinations are critical for ensuring safety and efficacy [Chen Y et al., 2021].

Piperine is used in the ancient Indian medication 'Trikatu' to boost drug bioavailability. Piperine inhibits EGCG glucuronidation and alters the pharmacokinetics of phenyl-butazone, improving absorption and bioavailability for cancer prevention. When piperine and curcumin are taken together, their bioavailability increases, resulting in synergistic benefits. In prostate cancer cells, different apoptotic pathways are implicated in the combined therapy of genistein and -lapachone; the principal target of this apoptotic mechanism is NAD(P)H dehydrogenase quinone 1 (NQO1). Synergy between leucovorin and 5-FU is an example of how interactions at different receptor sites; can either accelerate or inhibit activities. In most of the instances, interactions between receptors at the same location are inhibitory [Dudhatra GB et al., 2012].

PHY906 inhibited irinotecan-induced weight loss in mouse Colon 39 tumour models, allowing mice to tolerate otherwise lethal doses. When compared to irinotecan alone, the combination of irinotecan with PHY906 dramatically improved anticancer activity and overall survival. PHY906 demonstrated additive antitumor efficacy when coupled with leucovorin (LV), irinotecan, and 5-FU without increasing host toxicity. A further clinical trial on advanced colorectal cancer patients looked at PHY906's safety and tolerability in combination with weekly irinotecan, bolus 5-FU, and LV, and found no changes in medication pharmacokinetics [Kummar S et al., 2011].

5-FU is used in conjunction with other cytotoxic drugs, side effects are reduced, and response rates are increased. When administered in conjunction with dasatinib and 5-fluorouracil and oxaliplatin (FOLFOX) therapy, Curcumin increases capecitabine's proapoptotic and antimetastatic actions and inhibits tumour formation when combined with

bevacizumab. A Phase I trial demonstrated the antiproliferative effect of curcumin plus FOLFOX on colorectal cancer (CRC) cells. Resveratrol improves the sensitivity of colorectal cancer lines to 5-FU-induced oxidative stress by interacting with etoposide, mitomycin, 5-FU, and curcumin. Clinical studies shows that resveratrol reduces tumour cell development in colorectal cancer patients, making it a safe and effective chemo-preventive medication in combination therapy [Wei Y et al., 2018].

4.3 Cell Proliferation Inhibitors

Cancer remains one of the most challenging areas in medicine. Despite the availability of different therapeutic options such as surgery, radiation, chemotherapy, hormone therapy, and biological therapy, the development of new anticancer drugs is still lacking in wholistic treatment options. In the quest for effective cancer therapies and preventative techniques, herbal medicines have emerged as a viable path. These herbal remedies, which are high in phytochemicals such as phenolic compounds, terpenoids, lignans, tannins, and alkaloids, have been shown to have strong antioxidant properties that can suppress cell proliferation while also stimulating the immune system [Tran N et al., 2020].

Plant chemicals that may be used as cancer treatments inhibit the proliferation of cells. Flavonoids are an exciting class of natural compounds that inhibit cell proliferation. Many kinds of fruits, vegetables, and plants include flavonoids, which are polyphenolic compounds. The ability of specific flavonoids, such as quercetin, kaempferol, and apigenin, to inhibit cell proliferation has been studied [Tungmunnithum D et al., 2018]. Quercetin, for example, can be found in apples, onions, and tea. It has been shown to have anti-proliferative characteristics via cell cycle disruption, induction of apoptosis (programmed cell death), and prevention of angiogenesis, the process by which new blood vessels form to provide nutrition to tumors [Li Y et al., 2016]. The turmeric plant produces Curcumin, has an additional advantageous herbal component. One of curcumin's most well-studied anti-cancer properties is its propensity to reduce cell growth. It can alter several molecular processes in cell cycle control, apoptosis, and inflammation [Sharifi-Rad J et al., 2020].

Green tea polyphenols, including epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), have also been shown to inhibit cell proliferation. Green tea contains a high concentration of catechins, and EGCG, in particular has been researched for possible anti-cancer effects, such as apoptosis induction and cell growth suppression [Singh BN et al., 2011]. For example, BZL101, an extract of the aerial section of *Scutellaria barbata*, has shown promise in advanced breast cancer patients, while PHY906 has shown promise in treating advanced hepatocellular carcinoma. Furthermore, there are no particular cancer kinds for which herbal medication can be used for cancer prevention or treatment. Herbal medicine has been shown to exhibit anti-cancer properties in a variety of tumour types, including breast, colorectal, and pancreatic cancer [Marconett CN et al., 2010].

Herbal remedies have demonstrated encouraging promise in treating and preventing multiple cancers. They can be an invaluable supplement to traditional treatments, improving patient outcomes and raising the standard of living for cancer patients. Because they include a wide variety of phytochemicals, herbal medicines have the potential to stop cancer from starting and spreading by blocking the growth of cells and altering essential signalling pathways that lead to apoptosis.

4.4 Apoptotic Agents

Panaxadiol, a diol-type ginsenoside, boosts anticancer drug efficacy by regulating the cell cycle and triggering apoptosis. A significant element is programmed cell death, which involves caspase proteases. It may contribute significantly to the antiproliferative effect of irinotecan on colorectal cancer cells when combined with panaxadiol [Li X et al., 2009]. A traditional medicinal fungus called *Cordyceps militaris* has emerged as a possible cancer therapy. Through caspase pathways regulated by death receptors and mitochondria, its aqueous extract causes apoptosis in A549 cells. Furthermore, WECM suppresses hTERT transcriptional activity and lowers telomerase activity, which aids in the death of cancer cells [Phull A et al., 2022].

Ganoderma lucidum (GLT) triterpene extract, which contains over 200 active triterpenoids, including ganoderic acids, inhibits farnesyl protein transferases, which are required for the activation of the Ras oncoprotein, which is required for cell transformation. GLT inhibits tumour growth HT-29 cell proliferation, and promotes apoptosis and G0/G1 cell cycle arrest in colon cancer models. GLT also induces autophagy via the synthesis of Beclin-1 and LC-3 proteins, mediated by p38 MAPK inhibition [Thyagarajan A et al., 2010]. In a mouse model, 6-shogaol, a bioactive molecule derived from ginger, inhibits NCI-H1650 lung cancer cell development, lowering proliferation and triggering apoptosis. In vitro, 6-shogaol inhibits Akt signalling by targeting Akt1 and Akt2. Intraperitoneal 6-shogaol therapy reduces tumour weight in a prostate cancer mouse model, which is related to lower levels of pSTAT3Y705, cyclin D1, and survivin [Kim MO et al., 2014].

Alliin, a crucial garlic component, suppresses the growth of cholangiocarcinoma (CCA). In a mouse model, Alliin inhibits HuCCT-1, a liver bile duct cancer. Molecularly, it inhibits Matrix metalloproteinases -2 and 9 (MMP-2 and -9) signalling, as well as migration, invasion, and Epithelial-mesenchymal transitions (EMT). Alliin activates caspases, causing death, and changes tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinases (TIMP)/MMP balance in lung cancer cells, inhibiting adhesion and migration via the PI3K/AKT [Deng Y, et al., 2023]. In mice (40 mg/kg), alpinum isoflavone (AIF) from *Derris Eriocarpa* inhibits 786-O clear cell renal cell carcinoma (ccRCC). Reduced Akt signalling via lowered p-Akt/t-Akt ratio and RLIP76 expression and increased miR-101 expression [Wang et al., 2017]. AIF increases radiosensitivity in esophageal squamous cell carcinoma (ESCC) by causing ROS, DNA damage, apoptosis, and cell cycle arrest. It also inhibits Nrf2 and Nrf2-dependent antioxidants, NQO-1, and HO-1 [Choudhari AS et al., 2019].

Apigenin (APG), a naturally occurring flavonoid found in fruits and vegetables, has a variety of anticancer effects. APG suppresses human chondrosarcoma xenograft growth at 5 mg/kg by decreasing Ki67 expression and triggering apoptosis. APG controls Bcl-2 family proteins, activates caspases, and causes G2/M phase arrest. APG targets

dipeptidyl peptidase-IV (DPP-IV) in NSCLC xenografts (3 mg/kg), decreasing snail/slug signalling and downregulating DPP-IV, limiting EMT and invasion in both epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) positive and negative cells. When coupled with chemotherapeutic medicines or loaded in nanocarriers, APG exhibits potential synergy in cancer treatment, potentially increasing efficacy [Shankar E et al., 2017].

Natural flavonoids from *Scutellaria baicalensis*, baicalein and baicalin, suppress human colon cancer in NSG mice (50 mg/kg). They cause apoptosis by inhibiting hTERT and inactivating the p38, ERK, and MAPK pathways. In a nude mouse colon cancer model, baicalin (50 mg/kg) suppresses c-Myc and oncomiRs. When combined with docetaxel (10 mg/kg), baicalein (50 mg/kg) suppresses tumour development by increasing apoptosis and decreasing angiogenesis. These findings point to baicalein and baicalin as prospective anti-colon cancer medicines, either alone or in conjunction with currently available chemotherapeutics [Dou J et al., 2018].

Curcumin, a phenolic acid derivative of turmeric, has strong chemopreventive benefits as well as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anti-cancer capabilities. Extensive preclinical research backs up its anticancer effectiveness in various malignancies in vitro and animal models. Curcumin inhibits colon cancer cell invasion, reduces inflammatory indicators, inhibits cell proliferation, induces apoptosis-related protein expression, and prevents metastasis via lowering Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and matrix metalloproteases. Curcumin's broad activities make it a prospective therapeutic agent for modulating tumour development progression across various cancer types [Sharifi-Rad J et al., 2020].

4.5 Tumour Neovascularization Inhibitors

Angiogenesis, controlled by various variables, results in the formation of new blood vessels, whereas neovascularization, which occurs frequently in tumors, suggests defective tissue expansion. Recent research has revealed the anti-angiogenic potential of herbal remedies, with isoliquiritigenin, a chalconoid found in Licorice roots, being identified as one of 19 substances. It is efficient against pathological

neovascularization, and its mechanism has been studied *in vivo* [Liu Z et al., 2023].

In this study, 19 substances derived from traditional Chinese medicine herbs, including baicalein and tanshinone IIA, were found to have varying effects on human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) proliferation. Tanshinone IIA and isoliquiritigenin demonstrated substantial anti-proliferative actions without causing apoptosis, making them promising for the treatment of neovascularization illness. Isoliquiritigenin suppressed ERK1/2 phosphorylation in HUVECs in a dose-dependent manner, consistent with its anti-proliferative and anti-migration activities, although overall ERK expression remained unaltered [Yang L et al., 2014].

The researchers investigated the effect of Buyang Huanwu decoction (BYHWD) on hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) in nude mice. BYHWD reduced lung metastases without significantly reducing tumour weight or volume. Notably, it influenced angiogenesis-related factors (VEGF, RGS-5, and HIF-1), implying that BYHWD may influence the tumour microenvironment and vascular homeostasis of HCC, limiting angiogenesis and metastasis [Min L et al., 2016].

The study tested with JH, produced from the traditional Chinese medicinal herb *Coptis chinensis*, as an antimetastatic drug against human metastatic melanoma cells (C8161). JH inhibited cell growth in a dose-dependent manner without triggering apoptosis. JH inhibited neovascularization *in vitro* and *in vivo* by causing cell cycle arrest at G0/G1, upregulating p21 and p27, and inhibiting VE-cadherin expression. These data point to JH as a possible anti-melanoma medication candidate with low toxicity [Fu M et al., 2022]. The Hey1B ovarian cancer cell line was used in the study to investigate lycorine hydrochloride (LH) as an anti-ovarian cancer agent. LH substantially suppressed Hey1B cell growth while causing G2/M cell cycle arrest by increasing p21 and decreasing cyclin D3. LH also inhibited *in-vitro* capillary-like tube formation and *in vivo* ovarian cancer cell-driven neovascularization in Hey1B cells, as well as angiogenic gene expression (VE-cadherin, VEGF, Sema4D) and Akt activation. These data

points confirm LH as a viable anti-ovarian cancer medication option [Cao Z et al., 2023].

4.6 Multi-Drug Resistance (MDR) Protein Inhibitors

Excessive JWXYS dosages may decrease P-gp, hence boosting drug retention and combating P-gp-mediated multidrug resistance (MDR). By reducing P-gp expression, several herbal extracts reverse P-gp-mediated MDR. Concurrent JWXYS administration improves 5-FU efficacy by lowering P-gp expression, potentially increasing treatment results in cancer cells against MDR [Karthika C et al., 2022]. MDR in cancer is a big obstacle, but ginseng extracts, notably protopanaxatriol ginsenosides, shows promise in overcoming P-gp-mediated MDR by inhibiting P-gp, increasing intracellular drug accumulation, and decreasing MDR-1 mRNA levels. Shengmai improves anticancer drug sensitivity by decreasing MDR-1 mRNA levels. Ginsenosides Rh4 and Rk3 diminish cisplatin-induced nephrotoxicity, but ginsenoside Rd may protect against cisplatin-induced kidney injury by suppressing apoptosis. Ginseng use in conjunction with anticancer treatments may help reduce drug-induced toxicity, spurring greater investigation into their function, structure-activity correlations, and broader therapeutic implications [Baek S et al., 2017].

Recent studies on natural compounds combating chemoresistance reveal their ability to inhibit multidrug resistance (MDR) proteins or reduce MDR protein expressions. Notably, silybin from *Silybum marianum* allows doxorubicin to overcome resistance in colorectal cancer by inhibiting the expression of glucose transporter 1 (GLUT1)—polyoxypregnanes from *Marsdenia tenacissima* combat doxorubicin resistance in MDR cancer cell lines by inhibiting ABC transporters. P-gp inhibition by bis-benzylisoquinoline alkaloids increases doxorubicin accumulation and cytotoxicity in breast cancer cells. *Claviceps purpurea* ergot alkaloids may overcome chemoresistance via unknown signalling mechanisms in a variety of malignancies. In ovarian cancer, ellagic acid and resveratrol inhibit cisplatin resistance. Stilbenoids (Z)-3,4,30,50-tetramethoxystilbene and resveratrol improve cisplatin effectiveness in resistant

osteosarcoma cells. β -Phenylethyl isothiocyanate and 6-gingerol reduce glutathione (GSH) levels in uterine sarcoma cells, restoring doxorubicin and cisplatin resistance. Combining herbal substances with current medicines may be beneficial in the treatment of recurring malignancies [Mrusek M et al., 2015].

Cancer is a major concern worldwide, and while chemotherapy is important, multidrug resistance (MDR) is a significant barrier. The effects of *Ganoderma lucidum*, an edible mushroom used in traditional Chinese medicine, on drug-resistant liver cancer cells have been studied. Only the ethanol extract obtained from *G. lucidum* was capable of reversing drug resistance and inhibiting P-gp function *in-vitro*. It also effectively reversed paclitaxel resistance in mice, implying that it could overcome multidrug resistance in the treatment of hepatocellular carcinoma [Unlu A et al., 2016]. Drug inactivation, target modifications, membrane transporter alterations, apoptosis/autophagy dysregulation, the roles of the epithelial-mesenchymal transition and cancer stem cells, and other recognized cellular/molecular pathways must all be considered to understand drug resistance. Andrographolide, a major component of *Andrographis paniculata*, has been studied for potential anti-cancer activities. Co-administration with 5-FU overcomes drug resistance by downregulating P-170 and causing apoptosis [Vetvicka V et al., 2021].

Salvia miltiorrhiza constituents induce apoptosis, with dihydrotanshinone and cryptotanshinone causing p53-independent cytotoxicity and inducing autophagy in SW620/AD300 cells. Cryptotanshinone promotes autophagy in CRC cells via the ROS-p38-MAPK-NF- κ B signalling pathway. By increasing ROS levels, triggering apoptosis, and decreasing p-gp expression, salvianolic acid B reverses MDR in HCT8/VCR cells [Cheng Y et al., 2021].

Curcumin, a major component of turmeric, has potent anti-tumour activities at various stages of colorectal cancer (CRC). It reduces MRP and p-gp expression, changes the stemness of CRC cells, regulates drug transporter expression, and increases susceptibility to vincristine, cisplatin, and fluorouracil. Vincristine and curcumin have synergistic effects in xenograft mice by suppressing pro-survival genes such as MRP1.

Dihydromyricetin, a key component of the Chinese vine tea plant *Ampelopsis grossedentata*, exhibits anti-tumour effects and reverses chemoresistance in HCT 116/L-OHP cells by blocking MRP2 expression, activity, and the regulator's nuclear translocation against OXA [Li H et al., 2017].

Panax notoginseng, which is high in saponins, has anti-tumour effects. Its saponins have anti-tumour and anti-metastatic properties in colorectal cancer. Ginsenoside Rh2 causes apoptosis, slows migration, and promotes epithelial-mesenchymal transition in 5-FU-resistant HCT8 and LoVo cells while having no effect on MRP1, MDR1, or GST levels [Zhao H et al., 2017].

4.7 Cell Efflux Inhibitors

ABCB1 overexpression in malignancies causes MDR, making anticancer medicines ineffective. Despite decades of research, clinically licensed ABCB1 inhibitors for MDR remain scarce due to selectivity and toxicity concerns. To solve this issue, researchers are looking into repurposing existing pharmaceuticals like tariquidar. In this environment, polyoxypregnanes (POPs) from *Marsdenia tenacissima* appear as novel pro-drugs. POPs altered by microbiota release compounds that restore chemosensitivity in ABCB1-overexpressing cancer cells. These compounds avoid enzyme interactions by acting as selective, non-competitive ABCB1 inhibitors with different binding sites. Repeated doses of paclitaxel have a consistent pharmacokinetic interaction, promoting tumour accumulation and overcoming ABCB1-mediated chemoresistance. In combinational chemotherapy, POPs show promising benefits as effective and safe prodrugs for ABCB1-mediated MDR [Wu X et al., 2021].

Hernandezine identified as a potent ABCB1 inhibitor in a screening of 502 natural chemicals, demonstrating excellent interaction and selectivity in calcein-AM accumulation experiments on MDR19-HEK293 cells. With an IC₅₀ of around 300 nM for inhibition of ABCB1-mediated calcein-AM transport, hernandezine has shown potential in ABCB1-related therapeutic interventions. Hernandezine also showed impressive reversal of ABCB1-mediated drug resistance in MDR19-HEK293 cells, sensitizing them to doxorubicin at doses ranging from 50 to 500 nM.

Despite overlapping substrate specificities, hernandezine demonstrated selectivity by not affecting ABCB1 or ABCG2, implying its potential as a specific regulator of ABCB1-mediated drug resistance [Hsiao S et al., 2016].

The *Apiaceae* or *Umbelliferae* family accounts for 13% of Thai herbs in the 2020 Thai Herbal Pharmacopoeia (THP), containing therapeutic properties in fruits, leaves, and rhizomes. The most common bioactives are volatile oils (28%), terpenoids (19%), flavonoids, and phenylpropanoids. Approximately 44% of these herbs may influence drug metabolism enzymes, decreasing CYP3A4 and CYP2D6. In *in-vitro*, certain herbs have been shown to inhibit P-glycoprotein and other efflux transporters [Jiso A et al., 2022].

Schisandrin B physically interacts with p-glycoprotein, reversing resistance to paclitaxel, anthracycline, and vincristine in K562/ADR, KBv200, and MCF-7/Adr cells. Caffeic acid efficiently overcomes tumour cell resistance to vincristine, paclitaxel, and doxorubicin, resulting in increased apoptosis. Glabratephrin, a prenylated flavonoid, improves doxorubicin efficacy in triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) via decreasing doxorubicin affinity for P-gp. P-gp and cytochrome P450 (CYP450) enzymes play critical roles in medication oral bioavailability and interactions. Berberine, a primary isoquinoline alkaloid in CR, exhibits biphasic effects on P-gp, activating it at low concentrations and inhibiting it at high quantities. CR and its isoquinoline alkaloids also inhibit CYP450s such as CYP3A4, CYP2D6, and CYP1A2 [Wu J et al., 2023].

4.8 Liver and Tumour Metabolism Inhibitors (Cytochrome P-450; CYP-450 inhibitors)

Using herbal treatments with chemotherapy drugs in parallel treatment is becoming more popular to prevent side effects and improve overall health. However, these results differ due to probable interactions with drug-metabolizing enzymes and transporters, particularly the cytochrome P450 enzyme family, which can result in positive, negative, or neutral effects.

Pharmacokinetic medication interactions are important when changing exposure to active or harmful components because they involve essential mechanisms in absorption and elimination pathways. These include Phase I metabolism (primarily oxidation, reduction, and hydrolysis by CYP), Phase II metabolism (conjugation, frequently by UGT), and active transporters such as P-gp. The interactions of key CYP isozymes, such as CYP3A4 and CYP2D6, have a considerable impact on medication clearance, making understanding their interactions critical for tailored treatment [Haefeli WE et al., 2014].

About a dozen enzymes, primarily from the CYP1, 2, and 3 families, contribute to drug metabolism, handling 70-80% of therapeutic medications. Liver-expressed CYPs 3A4, 2C9, 2C8, 2E1, and 1A2 play important roles, and their expression is influenced by genetic polymorphisms, xenobiotic induction, cytokine modulation, and other factors. Ethnicity-dependent multiallelic genetic variants have a major impact on CYPs 2D6, 2C19, 2C9, 2B6, 3A5, and 2A6, resulting in a variety of pharmacogenetic phenotypes that affect medication responses, efficacy, and dose requirements. Polymorphisms in CYPs 1A1, 1A2, 2C8, 2E1, 2J2, and 3A4 are less predictive in general, but new results show the significance of specific variants, such as those in regulatory genes or NADPH: cytochrome P450 oxidoreductase (POR) [Zhao M et al., 2021].

Jiawei Xiaoyao San (JWXYS) at high doses (2400mg/kg/day) increases 5-FU accumulation in the blood and brain, perhaps affecting the blood-brain barrier. It may inhibit CYP 1A2, lowering 5-FU metabolism and extending $t_{1/2}$. Pretreatment with Panax ginseng extract for ten days improves the elimination half-life of 5-FU by 58.8%, potentially extending therapeutic effects. While the specific mechanism is unknown, it appears that ginseng can affect medication exposure and interactions, including docetaxel. Ginsenosides in ginseng moderately inhibit several CYP enzymes at clinically relevant doses, according to *in vitro* research [Chiang M et al., 2015].

Echinacea, which has anti-cancer qualities, may interact with medications. It is derived from *Echinacea purpurea* and affects P-gp and CYP3A4,

influencing medication metabolism. Human studies shows that midazolam clearance increases by 34%, indicating potential interactions with anti-cancer medicines. In example, echinacea had a significant effect on etoposide, decreasing platelet count. Discontinuing echinacea avoided future complications, implying that CYP inhibition caused etoposide accumulation and myelosuppression.

Garlic contains allicin, which inhibits hormone metabolism by blocking CYP3A4-dependent synthesis. Supplementation lowered elimination by 36% in research on the effect of garlic on docetaxel pharmacokinetics, presumably increasing toxicity owing to docetaxel buildup. This corresponds to garlic inhibiting CYP enzymes involved in docetaxel metabolism.

Ginseng, a globally popular herbal product, is primarily sourced from *Panax ginseng*, *Panax quinquefolius*, and *Panax japonicus*. Its therapeutic claims, including energy boosting and immunomodulation, rely on anecdotal evidence. Ginsenosides, steroidal saponins, contribute to its pharmacological activity, with reported antioxidant, cardiovascular, immunomodulatory, anticarcinogenic, neurotransmitter modulation, and antimutagenic effects in vitro studies on ginseng's impact on drug-metabolizing enzymes and P-gp yield mixed findings. A study on eight volunteers showed significant reductions in midazolam's area under curve (AUC), and C_{max} , attributed to ginseng's inductive effect on CYP3A4/5. A case report linked imatinib-induced hepatotoxicity to concurrent use of a ginseng-containing energy drink, raising concerns about ginseng's role in clinically significant interactions with chemotherapeutic agents [Fasinu PS et al., 2019].

Despite being an uncommon herbal supplement, grapefruit has been shown to affect medication pharmacokinetics. Its juice includes strong CYP and P-gp inhibitors, which can interfere with many drugs. A study of 21 individuals found that grapefruit juice increased nilotinib levels by 60%, attributed to CYP inhibition. In one case study, a patient who took docetaxel with grapefruit juice had changed pharmacokinetics, indicating that docetaxel clearance

was likely inhibited due to CYP enzyme inhibition [Yin OQP et al., 2010].

Silymarin, which has possible anticancer qualities, is found in milk thistle, which is frequently used in cancer and HIV patients. In *in-vitro* investigations show that it inhibits CYP and phase 2 enzymes. Although clinical data on milk thistle-drug interactions are scarce, a study on irinotecan found no significant changes in pharmacokinetics despite milk thistle use, implying that possible interactions may be mild due to low silibinin concentrations [Delmas D et al., 2020].

St. John's wort, a popular antidepressant herb, includes hyperforin, a powerful inhibitor of neurotransmitter reuptake. It affects CYPs and drug transporters in vitro, increasing CYP2B6, CYP2C19, CYP2E1, and CYP3A4 while inhibiting CYP2C9 and CYP2D6. Herb-drug interactions have been discovered in clinical research, changing the pharmacokinetics of medications such as omeprazole, simvastatin, and cyclosporine. St. John's wort, reduces the AUC of docetaxel by 12%, accelerates irinotecan metabolism, reduces SN-38 levels by 42%, and considerably reduces imatinib exposure.

In a 12-healthy volunteers' study, St. John's wort enhanced imatinib clearance by 43% while decreasing exposure by 30%, resulting in a 31% decrease in plasma half-life and a 20% decrease in C_{max} . These effects, which were detected in all subjects, may increase the chance of therapeutic failure in cancer patients who uses St. John's wort in conjunction with treatment drugs [Frye RF et al., 2004].

Docetaxel, a cancer antimitotic drug, affects cellular activities. Cox et al., investigated the effect of garlic supplementation (3600g allicin) on docetaxel pharmacokinetics in individuals with metastatic breast cancer. Garlic did not affect docetaxel clearance. However, there was a substantial AUC ratio difference in patients with the CYP3A5*1A gene. Given the metabolism of docetaxel by CYP3A4 and 3A5, the study implies that garlic may modify docetaxel clearance in persons with specific genetic variants [He S et al., 2010]. Van Erp *et al.*, found that taking 200 mg of milk thistle thrice daily (TID) for four or twelve days did not affect irinotecan clearance in six cancer patients. Although milk thistle

marginally reduced the AUC ratio of SN-38 and irinotecan, the low silybin levels indicated a modest interaction potential with irinotecan metabolism [Erp NPHV et al., 2005].

4.9 Urinary Excretion Inhibitors

Indican, found in Chinese herbs like *Isatis indigotica*, *Polygonum tinctorium* and *Polygonum perfoliatum*, alters the pharmacokinetics of orally administered methotrexate (MTX). Indican's major metabolite, indoxyl sulfate (IS), inhibits organic anion transporters-1 (OAT-1), OAT-3, and multidrug resistance-associated protein-4 (MRP-4). In rats, IS decreases renal excretion of oral MTX. Renal excretion is vital for MTX elimination, facilitated by OAT-1, OAT-3, and MRP-4. Indican hampers MTX elimination, suggesting IS inhibits these anion transporters, impacting MTX renal excretion [Lin S et al., 2018].

Echinacea, known for its anti-cancer properties, could impact medication interactions. Derived from *Echinacea purpurea*, it modulates P-gp and CYP3A4, influencing drug metabolism. Human studies reveal a 34% increase in midazolam clearance, suggesting potential interactions with anti-cancer drugs [Tafazoli A, 2020].

4.10 Toxicity Modifiers:

Saffron extract activated the Akt/p70s6k and ERK1/2 pathways, lowering cardiomyocytic apoptosis in vitro with doxorubicin. Furthermore, autophagy induction by *Solanum nigrum* Linn. aqueous extract improved doxorubicin efficacy against colorectal and ovarian cancer [Chahine N et al., 2021]. Various herbal compounds aimed at mitigating the adverse effects of chemotherapy have been explored for their antioxidative and ROS-scavenging properties in both *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* studies. For instance, saffron extract demonstrated the activation of Akt/p70s6k and ERK1/2 pathways, reducing cardiomyocytic apoptosis. Additionally, compounds from traditional Chinese medicine, such as *Gegen Qinlian* decoction, showcased potential in ameliorating irinotecan toxicity by modulating the Keap1/Nrf2 pathway. Other studies highlighted the cardioprotective effects of anthocyanin from black rice, (-)-epigallocatechin gallate, indole-3-carbinol, and 3,30-

diindolylmethane, among others. These findings contribute to understanding the chemoprotective abilities of herbal compounds, offering potential strategies to minimize chemotherapy side effects and reduce required doses [Lu J et al., 2021]. Patients undergoing CRC chemotherapy, particularly with 5-FU and oxaliplatin, suffer from a variety of side effects that have an impact on their quality of life and treatment outcomes. Combining standard chemotherapy with *Ganoderma lucidum* polysaccharides (GLP), which have anti-inflammatory, hypoglycaemia, and anti-tumour effects, may provide a solution. GLP inhibits cancer cell growth by triggering apoptosis and reactivating mutant p53. The potential combination of chemotherapeutics with non-toxic natural substances such as GLP could increase therapy response and patient well-being, opening a new path for CRC treatment [Sohretoglu D et al., 2018].

Breast cancer patients commonly use LSC101, an herbal extract blend, to alleviate chemotherapy-induced problems. Clinical trials reveal that, it effectively reduces haematological toxicity, with mice models demonstrating enhanced blood cell counts when paired with doxorubicin. While the precise mechanisms are unknown, the interplay of medicinal components from multiple herbs in LSC101 is thought to provide synergistic effects. Individual plants, such as *Ophiopogon japonicus* and *Astragalus membranaceus*, have shown hematopoietic advantages on their own [Xu J et al., 2017].

TCM medicine *Shenqi Fuzheng* Injection (SFI) restores immunological function at the cellular and molecular levels, reducing myelosuppression and GI tract responses caused by chemotherapy and surgery. Clinical studies show higher CD83, CD80, and CD86 expressions in tumour tissues, implying that SFI has a role in immunological healing via stimulating dendritic cells (DCs). Another study using medicinal mushrooms and herbs shows that the combination can reduce chemotherapy-induced damage across multiple organs while also reducing cancer cell proliferation and invasion [Chen X et al., 2019]. The immunomodulatory effects of a traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) blend of rose geranium, *Ganoderma tsugae*, *Codonopsis pilosula*, and *Angelica sinensis*

(RG-CMH) are employed in breast cancer therapy. Although statistical significance between groups was not attained in an RCT, the RG-CHM intervention showed promise in reducing chemotherapy-induced leukopenia and immunological dysfunction [Ma H et al., 2013]. Polysaccharide-K (PSK) is a chemoimmunotherapy drug produced from Yunzhi. The randomized clinical trials (RCTs) show that it is effective as an adjuvant in treating gastric, oesophageal, colorectal, breast, and lung malignancies. PSK, as a biological response modulator, improves the body's ability to fight tumour progression via a variety of processes such as leukocyte activation, cytokine modulation, and antioxidant activity [Fisher M et al., 2002].

Ganoderma Lucidum, also known as Lingzhi, is used in TCM to improve health and lifespan. In clinical trials, its spore powder efficiently combats cancer-related fatigue in endocrine therapy-treated breast cancer patients, enhancing their overall well-being and quality of life. TNF-, IL-6, and liver/kidney function were all statistically significant impacts of the medication. *G. lucidum's* varied biological properties, including hepatoprotection, make it an attractive addition in cancer therapy. Triterpenoids in *G. lucidum* have been proven in *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* investigations to contribute to its immunomodulating, antioxidant, antimetastatic, and anticancer effects [Sheikha AFE, 2022].

One well-known herb in TCM for immune system stimulation is *Rhodiola algida*. In a clinical investigation, *R. algida* extracts were found to be effective in minimizing chemotherapy-induced mouth ulcers, stimulating lymphocyte proliferation, increasing serum levels of IL-2, IL-4, and GMC-SF, and hastening white blood cell recovery. Patients treated with *R. algida* had fewer and smaller oral ulcers, with no liver or renal problems, showing its potential as a concurrent therapy with chemotherapy to treat mouth ulcers [Loo WTY, 2010].

Scutellaria barbata extract, provided alongside chemotherapy to patients with metastatic breast cancer in a phase 1b clinical trial, shown promising safety and efficacy. Side effects such as AST increase, diarrhoea, tiredness, and discomfort were minimized. Cell proliferation was suppressed, cell-cycle arrest

was triggered, ROS production was promoted, poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP) was hyperactivated, and glycolysis was inhibited when the herb's components were combined with chemotherapy [Perez AT et al., 2010].

Uncaria tomentosa, often known as Utor Cat's Claw, is a medicinal herb used to cure a variety of ailments, including cancer. Its extracts include cytostatic and anti-inflammatory properties, which help to reduce the side effects of chemotherapy and radiation. It helps in the restoration of cellular DNA, as well as the prevention of mutations and cell damage caused by chemotherapy medications. Furthermore, *U. tomentosa's* modulates the activity of the immune system by promoting the proliferation of normal T and B lymphocytes and the modulation of certain cytokines, including IL-1, IL-6, and TNF- α [Araújo MDCS et al., 2012].

4.11. Other Applications as an Adjuvants

Aidi injection, when paired with chemotherapy, dramatically reduced the occurrences of chemotherapy-related leucopenia, neutropenia, and thrombocytopenia. Furthermore, when Aidi injection was combined with chemotherapy, there was a significant increase in patients with improved performance status (PS), as evidenced by lower Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group (ECOG) scores, compared to those receiving chemotherapy alone. The Aidi group had fewer incidences of worsening PS than the control group, resulting in a significant overall improvement in PS. PS was lower in patients with nodal or distant metastases, lower baseline ECOG scores, and hepatic impairment. In contrast, Aidi injection and prolonged treatment cycles were linked to increased PS. Aidi injection was found to be a major independent factor in both PS improvement and the reduction of numerous chemotherapy-related side effects [Zhao D et al., 2021].

Senqifuzheng (SQFZ) injection, derived from *Codonopsis pilosula* and astragali, boosts the body's defences in different malignancies, significantly boosting Karnofsky score (KPS) when paired with chemotherapy [Yao K et al., 2014]. In HT29 and SW480 colorectal cell lines, *ganoderma lucidum*,

whether given alone, apart, or in combination with 5-FU, rebooted mutant p53 [Jiang D et al., 2017].

In Tibetan medicine, *Rhodiola Algida*, a traditional tonic in Asian countries, is used for haemoptysis, cardiovascular illness, antifatigue, and pneumonia. Externally administered for injuries, burns, and scalds, it has immunomodulatory effects and improves recovery in breast cancer patients by increasing white blood cell count and decreasing ulcers without causing toxicity [Tao H et al., 2019].

Catechu, an extract of *Acacia catechu*, is used to treat tissue regeneration, wound healing, and mouth ulcers. It has anti-inflammatory properties when combined with the radix of *Scutellariae baicalensis*. Local catechu application outperformed norfloxacin in a clinical investigation for oral mucositis in chemotherapy patients. Kangfuxin, an extract of *Periplaneta americana* with anti-inflammatory and wound healing characteristics, controlled cytokine expression and revealed a lower prevalence of mouth mucositis in those receiving chemotherapy compared to saline gargling [Kumari M et al., 2022].

5. Any Case Studies (herbal drug plus chemotherapeutic) under Clinical Investigation

Chen et al. investigated the efficacy and side effects of Shengmai in combination with chemotherapeutic drugs in treating advanced non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC). The study included 63 patients with NSCLC in stages III, B, and IV who were given navelbine and cisplatin treatment. Using ginseng in conjunction with anticancer medications resulted in a 48.5% response rate in the treatment group and a 32.2% response rate in the control group, with median survival times of 13 months and 9 months, respectively [Chen S et al., 2014].

According to a meta-analysis of 278 records, chemotherapy alone did not significantly improve performance status when paired with compound Kushen, Kangai, or Kanglaite injections. Chemotherapy alone was not as effective in treating leucopenia as an aidi injection. Despite this, when CHIs were administered in conjunction with chemotherapy, there was no improvement in general clinical symptoms, nausea, or vomiting. The study

also discovered that the reduction of adverse drug reactions (ADRs) with Huachansu injection alone was not as successful as it was with chemotherapy. TCM contributes significantly to the overall care of pancreatic cancer by increasing immunity, decreasing toxicity, and improving clinical symptoms and functional status [Zhang D et al., 2017].

Rhodiola algida, a popular tonic in Asian countries, is used to treat haemoptysis, pneumonia, and cardiovascular illnesses. It also has antifatigue properties. Through the modulation of IL-2 in Th-1 cells and IL-4, IL-6, and IL-10 in Th-2 cells, it has immunomodulatory effects. Oral *Rhodiola algida* treatment led to a faster recovery of white blood cell count and fewer ulcers in a clinical evaluation of breast cancer patients. Because of its ability to reduce inflammation and promote wound healing in inflammatory and ulcerative illnesses, kangfuxin, an ethanolic extract of *Periplaneta americana*, is employed. Clinical applications for catechu, an *Acacia catechu* extract, include wound healing, oral ulcer rinse, tissue regeneration, and abscesses [Chiang H et al., 2015].

6. Challenges (Roadblocks) for herbal medicines as adjuvants with chemotherapeutics

Various phytochemical ingredients in herbal treatments, adulteration, and deforestation pose quality issues. Advanced control processes, adherence to standards, current analytical techniques, and pharmacognostic studies for global adoption are required to ensure safety and efficacy [Kumar A et al., 2023]. Plant-based anticancer compounds have a great promise for the development of new chemotherapeutics as well as the improvement of current ones. However, they have limitations such as low stability, solubility, and potential adverse effects. This research will provide information on phytochemical compounds used in cancer treatment, potential compounds in pre-clinical and clinical studies, and the major barriers to their utilization as therapeutic agents. It will also discuss possible remedies [Garcia-Oliveira P et al., 2021].

Preclinical research identifies drugs with anticancer activity and frequently collaborates with clinical researchers for human trials. Positive preclinical results, however, may not always translate to clinical

trial success, because in vitro exposure to high quantities of natural compounds is difficult to mimic in humans. Clinical studies are expensive and must be funded by organizations such as the National Centre for Complementary and Integrative Health, cancer foundations, and research institutes. More extensive

philanthropic funding finance investigations demonstrate prospective supplements' safety and efficacy [Choudhari AS et al., 2020]. Herbal drugs interactions with various Chemotherapeutics and their findings are described in Table no. 1.

Table 1: Herbal drugs interactions with various Chemotherapeutics and their findings

Sr. No	Herbal Drug/ Formulation	Chemical Constituents	Chemotherapeutics	Cancer type	Findings	Reference(s)
	Indican	Indoxyl sulfate	Methotrexate	-	Inhibitor of organic anion transporter (OAT) 1, OAT 3 and multidrug resistance-associated protein (MRP) 4	Lin S et al., 2018
	<i>Echinacea purpurea</i>	-	Etoposide, docetaxel	Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC)	Cytochrome P450 (CYP) 3A4 inhibitor, platelet count eventually reached, No pharmacokinetic alteration of drug	Modarai M et al., 2007
	Chinese Herbal Injections (CHI)	-	Paclitaxel-based chemotherapy	Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC)	Significantly higher efficacy and lower risk of ADRs for advance NSCLC patients than TBC alone	Mengwei Ni et al., 2020
	Turmeric	Curcumin	Paclitaxel, Chemotherapeutics	Breast cancer	Turmeric supplementation improved quality of life (QoL), brought about symptom palliation and increased hematological parameters in breast cancer patients. Improve hematological parameters. modulate the function	Kalluru H et al., 2022; Wen C et al., 2019

			Carboplatin, 5-FU, Doxorubicin, and Radiation	Lung cancer, Breast Cancer, and Colorectal Cancer	of human multidrug resistance protein 1 (ABCC1) (inhibition of efflux of two fluorescent substrates, calcein-AM, and P-glycoprotein. Potentiating chemotherapeutic efficacy. curcumin promotes chemotherapy through regulating the expression or activity of the transcription factor NF- κ B. This finding implies that curcumin might target upstream signaling modulators of NF- κ B.	
	Huisheng	-	Platinum-Based Chemotherapy (Cisplatin, Carboplatin and Oxaliplatin)	NSCLC	Lower toxicity to white blood cell, lower platelet toxicity and reduced incidence of vomiting	Huang J et al., 2020
	Ginger	-	Adriamycin-cyclophosphamide regimen	Breast Cancer	Reducing nausea severity in breast cancer patients, Decrease circulating levels of C-reactive protein (CRP), high sensitivity C-reactive protein (hs-CRP), tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), soluble intercellular adhesion molecule	Choi J et al., 2022

					(sICAM), and interleukin-6 (IL-6) concentrations	
	Elemene Injection	-	Platinum-based chemotherapy	NSCLC	Improves disease control rate (DCR) and the objective Response rate (ORR), survival rate, quality of life (QOL), cellular immune function and can reduce severe toxicities. Elemene injection can improve clinical efficacy, enhance cellular immune function and alleviate the toxicity of chemotherapy	Wang X et al., 2019
	Aidi Injection	-	Paclitaxel-based chemotherapy	NSCLC	Significantly improve the clinical efficacy and QOL in patients with advanced NSCLC. Aidi injection can relieve the risk of hematotoxicity, gastrointestinal toxicity and liver injury in patients with NSCLC receiving paclitaxel-based chemotherapy. Aidi injection may have attenuation and synergistic efficacy to paclitaxel-based chemotherapy. low risk of neutropenia, thrombocytopenia	Xiao Z et al., 2019

					, and nausea/vomiting.	
	Aidi Injection	-	Docetaxel-Based Chemotherapy	NSCLC	Significantly improve the clinical efficacy and QOL in NSCLC. It may also have low risk of hematotoxicity, gastrointestinal toxicity, and low risk of inducing hepatorenal dysfunctions. Aidi injection may have attenuation and synergistic efficacy to docetaxel chemotherapy.	Xiao Z et al., 2018
	Jia-Wei-Xiao-Yao-San	-	Paclitaxel	NSCLC, breast cancer, and pancreatic cancer	Plasma AUC of paclitaxel, half-life of paclitaxel increased and the clearance increased approximately 1.4-fold compared to paclitaxel alone	Cheng Y et al., 2018
	Jia-Wei-Xiao-Yao-San	-	5-FU	Colorectal cancer	P-gp inhibition	Wen C et al., 2019
	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	-	Doxorubicin	-	Diminish the adverse effects of doxorubicin. increases in the AUC and half-life of doxorubicin upon concurrent administration with curcumin, enhanced the absorption of doxorubicin	Lin J et al., 2003

					and reduced the drug efflux of doxorubicin, inhibits the P-gp Pre-clinical: Inhibits carcinogenesis and modulates chemo-resistance and radio-resistance Clinical: Potentiates the anti-tumor effect of chemotherapeutic agents	
	<i>Radix Astragali</i> (<i>Astragalus propinquus</i> , Huangqi)	-	IL-2 therapy	Murine renal carcinoma cells	Enhancing the anticancer activity of recombinant IL-2-generated lymphokine-activated killer (LAK) cells on murine renal carcinoma cells and reducing the severe side effects of recombinant IL-2 therapy (e.g. acute renal failure, capillary leakage syndrome, myocardial infarction, and fluid retention) in the treatment of cancer patients. Pre-clinical: Stimulates the production of IL-6 and TNF and enhances the activity of LAK cells	Zhao L et al., 2022

					Clinical: Potentiates the activity of chemotherapeutic agents, prolongs survival, reduces the adverse toxicity of chemo- or radio-therapy.	
	Ginseng	Triterpene glycosides, Ginsenosides	5-FU	Colorectal Cancer	Pre-clinical: Inhibits cancer growth and potentiates the anti-tumor effect of chemotherapeutic agents Clinical: Potentiates the anti-tumor effect of chemotherapeutic agents and attenuates the adverse toxicity of chemo- or radio-therapy increasing the anticancer effects enhance the cytotoxicity of several chemotherapeutic agents, Inhibition of nuclear factor-kappa (NF- κ B) may be one of the potential mechanisms of the observed effect. synergistic inhibitory effect, Ginseng extracts may induce chemosensitization of conventional anticancer agents via downregulation	Chen S et al., 2014; El-Sebaey AM et al., 2019
		Ginsenosides	Irinotecan, Mitomycin C, Docetaxel, Cisplatin, Cisplatin, and Doxorubicin			

					of MDR-1 expression (P-gp inhibition)	
	Garlic	Allicin, Alliin	Cisplatin and Cyclophosphamide	Head and neck cancer and non-hodgkin's lymphoma	Shown to markedly suppress the cisplatin-induced elevation in the level of inflammation cytokines including TNF-, IL-1, TGF-1, COX-2 and iNOS clearly indicating that SAMC exerted an anti-inflammatory effect in cisplatin-induced renal injury as well as hepatotoxicity in rat model. Potent against cyclophosphamide-induced toxicity.	Tai C et al., 2013
	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>		Cytotoxicity of Cisplatin, Doxorubicin, Docetaxel, and 5-FU Cisplatin-, Doxorubicin-, and Docetaxel	Human Colorectal Carcinoma Cells DLD-1 and HT-29 human colorectal carcinoma Cells Human Ovarian Carcinoma Cells (ES-2, SKOV-3, and OVCAR-3 human ovarian cancer cell lines)	Induced autophagy via microtubule-associated protein 1 light chain 3 A/B II accumulation but not caspase-3-dependent apoptosis in both cell lines. combined drug effect with all tested drugs by enhancing cytotoxicity in tumor cells. Promoted tumor suppression efficiency of cisplatin, doxorubicin, and docetaxel in the	Wang C et al., 2015; Liu L et al., 2019

					scavenging, accompanied by the regulation of Bcl-2, Bax, c-myc, and p53 genes. BBR could protect the liver from the damage caused by DOX.	
	<i>Alpinia galanga L.</i>	Galangal	Doxorubicin Cisplatin	4T1 cells Hepatocellular carcinoma	Increased the cytotoxic effect of Dox, suppressed the expression of MMP-9 induced by Dox Enhanced hepatic function and oxidative stress markers, effect is more potent than the treatment with CP alone in rats. Our study suggested that AORE can be used as a promising natural chemoprevention or a chemosensitizing agent against hepatocarcinogenesis	Zhang T et al., 2021
	<i>Rheum tanguticum</i>	Polysaccharides	Radiation	Intestine	Protect the intestinal cells from radiation-induced damage via the regulation of Nrf2 and its downstream protein HO-1.	Wang K et al., 2022
	TJ-41 (Bu-Zhong-Yi-Qi-Tang)	-	Radiation chemotherapy	Intestine	Protection of the intestine and hematopoietic organs against radiation damage,	Liu S et al., 2012

					beneficial effects on cancer-related fatigue and quality of lives in cancer patients	
	PHY906 [74, 88–90],	-	CPT-11 (Irinotecan, Camptosar®) Capecitabine CPT-11/5-FU/LV VP-16 L-OddC Gemcitabine Oxaliplatin Sorafenib Taxol Sunitinib Irinotecan, 5-fluorouracil (5-FU), and leucovorin (LV)	Colorectal cancer Colorectal and liver cancer Colorectal cancer Lung cancer Leukemia, pancreatic cancer Pancreatic cancer Colorectal cancer Renal and liver cancer Lung, breast, and ovarian cancer Renal and liver cancer Colorectal Cancer	reduce the dose-limiting GI side effect (severe late-onset diarrhea) of CPT-11, PHY906 can also restore damaged intestinal epithelium through promotion of intestinal progenitor or stem cell growth, mediated by increasing of several Wnt signaling components as well as potentiation of Wnt action, PHY906 was shown to provide cytoprotective effects without dampening the anti-tumor activity of chemotherapeutic agents in liver, pancreatic, and colorectal cancer patients under chemotherapy. Modulator of the weekly, bolus regimen of irinotecan, 5-FU, and LV (IFL)	Qin T et al., 2008

	Huachansu Dried toad skin extract	-	Gemcitabine-Oxaliplatin	Advanced gallbladder carcinoma	Improving the QOL of patients with advanced GBC. Reduced Nonhematologic toxicity	Liu J et al., 2019
	Kanglaite	-	Mitomycin (MMC)/cisplatin (DDP)	Advanced breast cancer	Excellent safety profile of the MMC/DDP combination, reduced the toxicity induced by chemotherapy or radiotherapy	Cao A et al., 2019
	Astragalus	-	Platinum-based chemotherapy	Non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC)	Increase chemotherapy efficacy and reduce toxicity, shown to have immunologic benefits by stimulating macrophage and natural killer cell activity and inhibiting T-helper cell type 2 cytokines.	Zhang F et al., 2009
	Wortmannin fungal metabolite	-	Roscovitine	Different types of cancer	Wortmannin increases roscovitine-induced apoptosis in a dose-dependent manner, which was correlated with the inhibition of phosphorylated PKB/Akt level. Wortmannin enhances the effects of roscovitine by causing a pronounced reduction of mitochondrial membrane	Bahmani F et al., 2018

					potential (MMP) and increases of cytochrome c release and active caspase-3, as well as enhances the activation of Bax and Bad, including Bax oligomerization and the mitochondrial translocation of Bax and Bad. Taken together, these results provide evidence for the potential application of a roscovitine and wormannin combination in clinical treatment for solid tumours.	
	<i>Centaurea albonitens</i>	-	Leukaemia cell lines Colorectal cancer and ovarian cancer	Vincristine Doxorubicin	Significantly enhance the cytotoxicity, without increasing toxicity. Reduce the cardiotoxicity and resistance, synergistic effects	Xiong S et al., 2018; Emadi SA et al., 2022
	<i>Silybum marianum</i> (milk thistle)	Silybin (silibinin), silychristine,	Colorectal PC-3 Prostate Cancer Cells	Doxorubicin	To overcome drug by inhibiting glucose transporter 1 (GLUT1) expression. Additive effect on DXR cytotoxicity Protective influence on the heart and liver tissue against toxicity induced by doxorubicin	Gioti K et al., 2019

			Liver		Alleviate doxorubicin-induced toxicity on various biochemical and hematological parameters, regulation of COX1 gene expression level as well as decreasing plasma and liver TBARS and increasing total antioxidant capacity, reduced GSH, GST, and GPx that minimized oxidative stress induced by the drug	
	Kang' ai injection (Ginseng (<i>Panax ginseng</i> C.A. Mey. [Araliaceae]), milkvetch root (<i>Astragalus membranaceus</i> [Fisch.] Bunge [Fabaceae]), and Kushen (<i>Sophora flavescens</i> Ait.))	-	Colon cancer	Irinotecan hydrochloride injection	Increase pharmacokinetic (increase plasma drug concentration)	Chen Y et al., 2023
	Berberine (BER)	Berberine (BER)	Powerful cytotoxicity against A549 lung cancer cells	Etoposide (ETP)	High BER and ETP entrapment efficiency	Czylkowska A et al., 2021

	<i>Piper nigrum</i> <i>L.</i>	-	Ovarian CHO-K1 Cells	Doxorubicin	Increased the cytotoxicity and reduced the genotoxicity of doxorubicin	Sari NF et al., 2018
	Kushen Injection (Rhizom, Heterosmila cis Japonicae and <i>Sophora</i> <i>flavescens</i>)	-	Pancreatic cancer	GEM treatment (5- FU, L-OHP)	-	Wang H et al., 2019

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Current pre-clinical and clinical evidences demonstrate the beneficial effects of natural medicines in a variety of diseases, especially cancer. Although, these beneficial effects are evident, the use of natural medicines in developing and developed countries are still lacking due to less established evidence of randomized clinical trials in support of regulatory approval. In this modern era, we need more support from regulatory authorities, local authorities, patient advocacy groups and other stakeholders to explore the therapeutic potential of this wealthy resources from the nature to lessen off-target secondary pharmacological toxicities from the modern medicine along with improvement of quality of life (QOL). Herbal medicines undeniably play a major role in treating from acute diagnosis to a chronic manageable disease. Ultimately, any decision on treating the cancer patient lies on the best prevailing evidence of controlled randomized clinical trials.

Abbreviations:

5-FU: 5-Fluorouracil

ABCB1: ATP-binding cassette sub-family B member 1

ABCG1: ATP binding cassette sub-family G member 1

ADI: Aidi Injection

ADME: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion

ADRs: Adverse Drug Reactions

AGP: α -acid glycoprotein

AIF: Alpinum Isoflavone

AMPK: AMP-activated protein kinase

AUC: Area Under Curve

BCRP: Breast Cancer Resistance Protein

BYHWD: Buyang Huanwu Decoction

CB1: Cannabinoid Receptor 1

CBD: Cannabidiol

CCA: Cholangiocarcinoma

CHMs: Chinese Herbal Medicines

Cmax: Concentration at Maximum

COX-2: Cyclooxygenase-2

CPT-11: Irinotecan

CRC: Colorectal Cancer

CRP: C-reactive protein

CYP-450: Cytochrome P450

D9-THC: D9-tetrahydrocannabinol

JWXYs: Jiawei Xiaoyao San

DCs: Dendritic Cells

KPS: Karnofsky score

DPP-IV: Dipeptidyl Peptidase-IV

LH: Lycorine Hydrochloride

DNA: Deoxyribonucleic acid

LV: Leucovorin

ECOG: Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group

MAPK: Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase

EGCG: Epigallocatechin Gallate

MDR1: Multidrug Resistant 1

EGFR: Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor

MMP: Matrix metalloproteinases

EMT: Epithelial-mesenchymal transitions

mRNA: Messenger RNA

ESCC: Esophageal Squamous Cell Carcinoma

MRPs: Multidrug Resistance Proteins

eNOS: Endothelial NO synthase

MTX: Methotrexate

FTase: Farnesyl Protein Transferases

NF- κ B: Nuclear Factor- κ B

FOLFOX: 5-Fluorouracil and Oxaliplatin

NK: Natural Killer

GLC: Ganoderma Lucidum

NO: Nitric Oxide

GLT: Glucose Transporters

NSCLC: Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer

GLUT1: Glucose Transporter 1

NQO1: NAD(P)H Dehydrogenase Quinone 1

GM-CSF: Granulocyte-Macrophage Colony-Stimulating Factor

OAT-1: Organic Anion Transporters-1

GSH: Glutathione

P-gp: P-glycoprotein

HCC: Hepatocellular Carcinoma

PI3K-Akt: Phosphatidylinositol-3-kinase

HIF: Hypoxia-Inducible Factor

PARP: Poly (ADP-ribose) Polymerase

HIV: Human Immuno-Deficiency Virus

POPs: Polyoxypregnanes

HSA: Human Serum Albumin

PPAR γ : Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor-gamma

hTERT: Human Telomerase Reverse Transcriptase

PSK: Polysaccharide-K

HUVEC: Human Umbilical Vein Endothelial Cells

RCT: Randomized Clinical Trials

IFN- γ : Interferon- γ

RGS: Regulator of G-protein Signalling

IL-1: Interleukin-1

RNA: Ribonucleic Acid

IL-6: Interleukin-6

ROS: Reactive Oxygen Species

SCF: Stem Cell Factor

SULT: Sulfotransferases

t_{1/2}: Half-Life

TCM: traditional Chinese Medicine

T2DM: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

TGF- β : Transforming Growth Factor- β

THP: Thai Herbal Pharmacopoeia

TID: Thrice Daily

TIMP: Tissue Inhibitor of Metalloproteinases

TNBC: Triple-Negative Breast Cancer

TNF- α : Tumour Necrosis Factor- α

TRPV1: Transient Receptor Potential Vanilloid 1

VEGF: Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor

UCN-01: 7-hydroxystaurosporine

UGT: Uridine 5'-diphospho-glucuronosyltransferase

USFDA: U.S. Food and Drug Administration

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REFERENCES

1. Amalraj A, Pius A, Gopi S, Gopia S. Biological activities of curcuminoids, other biomolecules from turmeric and their derivatives – A review. *J Tradit Complement Med.* 2017; 7(2):205–233.
2. Araújo MDCS, Farias IL, Gutierrez J, Dalmora SL, Flores N, Farias J, et al. *Uncaria tomentosa*—Adjuvant Treatment for Breast Cancer: Clinical Trial. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.* 2012; 2012: 676984.
3. Baek S, Shin B, Kim NJ, Chang S, Park JH. Protective effect of ginsenosides Rk3 and Rh4 on cisplatin-induced acute kidney injury in vitro and in vivo. *J Ginseng Res.* 2017;41:233-239.
4. Bahmani F, Esmacili S, Bashash D, Dehghan-Nayeri N, Mashati P, Gharehbaghian A. *Centaurea albonitens* extract enhances the therapeutic effects of Vincristine in leukemic cells by inducing apoptosis. *Biomed Pharmacother.* 2018;99:598-607.
5. Bahmani F, Esmacili S, Bashash D, Dehghan-Nayeri N, Mashati P, Gharehbaghian A. *Centaurea albonitens* extract enhances the therapeutic effects of Vincristine in leukemic cells by inducing apoptosis. *Biomed Pharmacother.* 2018;99:598-607.
6. Bahmani F, Esmacili S, Bashash D, Dehghan-Nayeri N, Mashati P, Gharehbaghian A. *Centaurea albonitens* extract enhances the therapeutic effects of Vincristine in leukemic cells by inducing apoptosis. *Biomed Pharmacother.* 2018;99:598-607.
7. Bai J, Qi J, Yang Li, Wang Z, Wang R, Shi Y. A comprehensive review on ethnopharmacological, phytochemical, pharmacological and toxicological evaluation, and quality control of *Pinellia ternata* (Thunb.) Breit. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2022;298:115650.
8. Banyal A, Tiwari S, Sharma A, Chanana I, Patel SKS, Kulshrestha S, Kumar P. Vinca alkaloids as

- a potential cancer therapeutics: recent update and future challenges. *3 Biotech*; 2023:13.
9. Bracci L, Schiavoni G, Sistigu A, Belardelli F. Immune-based mechanisms of cytotoxic chemotherapy: implications for the design of novel and rationale-based combined treatments against cancer. *Cell Death Differ*. 2014;21(1):15-25.
 10. Brown JD, Rivera KJR, Hernandez LYC, Doenges MR, Auchey I, Pham T, et al. Natural and Synthetic Cannabinoids: Pharmacology, Uses, Adverse Drug Events, and Drug Interactions. *J Clin Pharmacol*. 2021;61:S37-S52.
 11. Cao A, He H, Wang Q, Li L, An Y, Zhou X. Evidence of Astragalus injection combined platinum-based chemotherapy in advanced nonsmall cell lung cancer patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2019;98(11):e14798.
 12. Cao Z, Yu D, Fu S, Zhang G, Pan Y, Bao M, et al. Lycorine hydrochloride selectively inhibits human ovarian cancer cell proliferation and tumor neovascularization with very low toxicity. *Toxicol Lett*. 2013;218:174-85.
 13. Chahine N, Nader M, Duca L, Martiny L, Chahine R. Saffron extracts alleviate cardiomyocytes injury induced by doxorubicin and ischemia-reperfusion in vitro. *Drug Chem Toxicol*. 2016;39(1):87-96.
 14. Chen S, Wang Z, Huang Y, O'Barr SA, Wong RA, Yeung S, et al. Ginseng and Anticancer Drug Combination to Improve Cancer Chemotherapy: A Critical Review. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2014; 2014: 168940.
 15. Chen S, Wang Z, Huang Y, O'Barr SA, Wong RA, Yeung S, et al. Ginseng and Anticancer Drug Combination to Improve Cancer Chemotherapy: A Critical Review. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2014; 2014:168940.
 16. Chen Y, Hu Z, Jiang J, Liu C, Gao S, Song M, et al. Evaluation of pharmacological and pharmacokinetic herb-drug interaction between irinotecan hydrochloride injection and Kangai injection in colorectal tumor-bearing mice and healthy rats. *Front Pharmacol*. 2023; 14: 1282062.
 17. Chen X, Qi S, Li Z, He B, Li HL, Fu J, Huang S, et al. Shenqi Fuzheng Injection (SFI) Enhances IFN- α Inhibitory Effect on Hepatocellular Carcinoma Cells by Reducing VEGF Expression: Validation by Gene Silencing Technique. *Biomed Res Int*. 2019 Apr 23;2019:8084109.
 18. Chen Y, Hu Z, Qi W, Gao S, Jiang J, Wang S, et al. Pharmacovigilance of herb-drug interactions: A pharmacokinetic study on the combination administration of herbal Kang'ai injection and chemotherapy irinotecan hydrochloride injection by LC-MS/MS. *J Pharm Biomed Anal*. 2021;194:113784.
 19. Cheng Y, Hung I, Liao Y, Hu W, Hung Y. *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Protects Endothelial Dysfunction against Mitochondrial Oxidative Stress. *Life (Basel)*. 2021;11(11): 1257.
 20. Cheng Y, Hsieh C, Tsai T. Concurrent administration of anticancer chemotherapy drug and herbal medicine on the perspective of pharmacokinetics. *J Food Drug Anal*. 2018;26(2S):S88-S95.
 21. Chiang H, Chen H, Wu C, Wu P, Wen K. *Rhodiola* plants: Chemistry and biological activity. *J Food Drug Anal*. 2015;23(3): 359–369.
 22. Chiang M, Chang L, Wang J, Lin L, Tsai T. Herb-drug pharmacokinetic interaction of a traditional chinese medicine jia-wei-xiao-yao-san with 5-Fluorouracil in the blood and brain of rat using microdialysis. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2015;2015:729679.
 23. Choi J, Lee J, Kim K, Choi H, Lee S, Lee H. Effects of Ginger Intake on Chemotherapy-Induced Nausea and Vomiting: A Systematic Review of Randomized Clinical Trials. *Nutrients*. 2022;14(23): 4982.
 24. Choudhari AS, Mandave PC, Deshpande M, Ranjekar P, Prakash O. Phytochemicals in Cancer Treatment: From Preclinical Studies to Clinical Practice. *Front Pharmacol*. 2019;10: 1614.
 25. Choudhari AS, Mandave PC, Deshpande M, Ranjekar P, Prakash O. Phytochemicals in Cancer Treatment: From Preclinical Studies to Clinical Practice. *Front Pharmacol*. 2020;10:1614.
 26. Czynkowska A, Szczesio M, Raducka A, Rogalewicz B, Kręcisz P, Czarnecka K, et al. Cytotoxic Activity against A549 Human Lung Cancer Cells and ADMET Analysis of New Pyrazole Derivatives. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2021;22(13):6692.
 27. Delmas D, Xiao J, Vejux A, Aires V. Silymarin and Cancer: A Dual Strategy in Both in

- Chemoprevention and Chemosensitivity. *Molecules*. 2020;25(9):2009.
28. Deng Y, Ho C, Lan Y, Xiao J, Lu M. Bioavailability, Health Benefits, and Delivery Systems of Allicin: A Review. *J Agric Food Chem*. 2023;71:19207-19220.
 29. Dou J, Wang Z, Ma L, Peng B, Mao K, Li E, et al. Baicalein and baicalin inhibit colon cancer using two distinct fashions of apoptosis and senescence. *Oncotarget*. 2018;9(28):20089-20102.
 30. Dudhatra GB, Mody SK, Awale MM, Patel HB, Modi CM, Kumar A, et al. A Comprehensive Review on Pharmacotherapeutics of Herbal Bioenhancers. *Scientific World Journal*. 2012; 2012: 637953.
 31. Efferth T, Li PCH, Konkimalla VSB, Kaina B. From traditional Chinese medicine to rational cancer therapy. *Trends Mol Med*. 2007;13(8):353-61.
 32. Efferth T, Li PCH, Konkimalla VSB, Kaina B. From traditional Chinese medicine to rational cancer therapy. *Trends Mol Med*. 2007;13(8):353-61.
 33. El-Sebaey AM, Abdelhamid FM, Abdalla OA. Protective effects of garlic extract against hematological alterations, immunosuppression, hepatic oxidative stress, and renal damage induced by cyclophosphamide in rats. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int*. 2019;26(15):15559-15572.
 34. Emadi SA, Rahbardar MG, Mehri S, Hosseinzadeh H. A review of therapeutic potentials of milk thistle (*Silybum marianum* L.) and its main constituent, silymarin, on cancer, and their related patents. *Iran J Basic Med Sci*. 2022; 25(10): 1166–1176.
 35. Erp NPHV, Baker SD, Zhao M, Rudek MA, Guchelaar H, Nortier JWR, et al. Effect of milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) on the pharmacokinetics of irinotecan. *Clin Cancer Res*. 2005;11(21):7800-6.
 36. Fasinu PS, Rapp GK. Herbal Interaction With Chemotherapeutic Drugs-A Focus on Clinically Significant Findings. *Front Oncol*. 2019;9:1356.
 37. Fisher M, Yang L. Anticancer effects and mechanisms of polysaccharide-K (PSK): implications of cancer immunotherapy. *Anticancer Res*. 2002;22(3):1737-54.
 38. Frye RF, Fitzgerald SM, Lagattuta TF, Hruska MW, Egorin MJ. Effect of St John's wort on imatinib mesylate pharmacokinetics. *Clin Pharmacol Ther*. 2004;76(4):323-9.
 39. Fu M, Liu Y, Cheng H, Xu K, Wang G. *Coptis chinensis* and dried ginger herb combination inhibits gastric tumor growth by interfering with glucose metabolism via LDHA and SLC2A1. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 2022;284:114771.
 40. Garcia-Oliveira P, Otero P, Pereira AG, Chamorro F, Carpena M, Echave J, et al. Status and Challenges of Plant-Anticancer Compounds in Cancer Treatment. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel)*. 2021;14(2):157.
 41. Gioti K, Papachristodoulou A, Benaki D, Havaki S, Beloukas A, Vontzalidou A, et al. Silymarin Enriched Extract (*Silybum marianum*) Additive Effect on Doxorubicin-Mediated Cytotoxicity in PC-3 Prostate Cancer Cells. *Planta Med*. 2019;85(11-12):997-1007.
 42. Gowthami R, Sharma N, Pandey R, Agrawal A. Status and consolidated list of threatened medicinal plants of India. *Genetic Resources and Crop Evolution*. 2021;68:2235–2263.
 43. Haefeli WE, Carls A. Drug interactions with phytotherapeutics in oncology. *Expert Opin Drug Metab Toxicol*. 2014;10(3):359-77.
 44. He L, Zhong Z, Chen M, Liang Q, Wang Y, Tan W. Current Advances in *Coptidis Rhizoma* for Gastrointestinal and Other Cancers. *Front Pharmacol*. 2021; 12: 775084.
 45. He S, Yang A, Li X, Du Y, Zhou S. Effects of herbal products on the metabolism and transport of anticancer agents. *Expert Opin Drug Metab Toxicol*. 2010;6(10):1195-213.
 46. Hsiao S, Lu Y, Yang C, Tuo W, Li Y, Huang Y, et al. Hernandezine, a Bisbenzylisoquinoline Alkaloid with Selective Inhibitory Activity against Multidrug-Resistance-Linked ATP-Binding Cassette Drug Transporter ABCB1. *J Nat Prod*. 2016;79(8):2135-42.
 47. Huang J, Wang Z, Xue H, Cao A, Turner C, Wang J, et al. Huisheng Oral Solution Adjunct with Platinum-Based Chemotherapy for the Treatment of Advanced Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer: A Meta-Analysis and Systematic Review. *Front Pharmacol*. 2020; 11: 476165.
 48. Huang X, Li X, Xie M, Huang Z, Huang Y, Wu G, et al. Resveratrol: Review on its discovery,

- anti-leukemia effects and pharmacokinetics. *Chem Biol Interact.* 2019;306:29-38.
49. Jarrar Y, Lee S. The Functionality of UDP-Glucuronosyltransferase Genetic Variants and their Association with Drug Responses and Human Diseases. *J Pers Med.* 2021; 11(6): 554.
 50. Jiang D, Wang L, Zhao T, Zhang Z, Zhang R, Jin J, et al. Restoration of the tumor-suppressor function to mutant p53 by Ganoderma lucidum polysaccharides in colorectal cancer cells. *Oncol Rep.* 2017;37(1):594-600.
 51. Jiso A, Khemawoot P, Techapichetvanich P, Soopairin S, Phoemsap K, Damrongsakul P, et al. Drug-Herb Interactions among Thai Herbs and Anticancer Drugs: A Scoping Review. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel).* 2022 ;15(2):146.
 52. Juvala A, Hamid AAA, Halim KBA, Hasa ATC. P-glycoprotein: new insights into structure, physiological function, regulation, and alterations in disease. *Heliyon.* 2022; 8(6): e09777.
 53. Kalluru H, Mallayasamy SR, Kondaveeti SS, Chandrasekhar V, Kalachaveedu M. Effect of turmeric supplementation on the pharmacokinetics of paclitaxel in breast cancer patients: A study with population pharmacokinetics approach. *Phytother Res.* 2022;36(4):1761-1769.
 54. Karthika C, Sureshkumar R, Zehravi M, Akter R, Ali F, Ramproshad S, et al. Multidrug Resistance of Cancer Cells and the Vital Role of P-Glycoprotein. *Life (Basel).* 2022;12(6): 897.
 55. Kim MO, Lee M, Oi N, Kim S, Bae KB, Huang Z, et al. [6]-shogaol inhibits growth and induces apoptosis of non-small cell lung cancer cells by directly regulating Akt1/2. *Carcinogenesis.* 2014;35(3):683-91.
 56. Kumar A, Nirmal P, Kumar M, Jose A, Tomer V, Oz E, et al. Major Phytochemicals: Recent Advances in Health Benefits and Extraction Method. *Molecules.* 2023;28(2): 887.
 57. Kumari M, Radha, Kumar M, Zhang B, Amarowicz R, Puri S, et al. Acacia catechu (L.f.) Willd.: A Review on Bioactive Compounds and Their Health Promoting Functionalities. *Plants (Basel).* 2022;11(22):3091.
 58. Kummar S, Copur MS, Rose M, Wadler S, Stephenson J, O'Rourke M, et al. A phase I study of the chinese herbal medicine PHY906 as a modulator of irinotecan-based chemotherapy in patients with advanced colorectal cancer. *Clin Colorectal Cancer.* 2011;10:85-96.
 59. Li H, Li Q, Liu Q, Yang K, Chen Z, Cheng Q, Wu L. The Versatile Effects of Dihydromyricetin in Health. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.* 2017; 2017:1053617.
 60. Li Y, Yao J, Han C, Yang J, Chaudhry MT, Wang S, Liu H, Yin Y. Quercetin, Inflammation, and Immunity. *Nutrients.* 2016;8(3):167.
 61. Li L, Leung PS. Use of herbal medicines and natural products: an alternative approach to overcoming the apoptotic resistance of pancreatic cancer. *Int J Biochem Cell Biol.* 2014;53:224-36.
 62. Li X, Wang C, Mehendale SR, Sun S, Wang Q, Yuan C. Panaxadiol, a purified ginseng component, enhances the anti-cancer effects of 5-fluorouracil in human colorectal cancer cells. *Cancer Chemother Pharmacol.* 2009;64:1097-104.
 63. Lin J, Dong H, Oppenheim JJ, Howard O. Effects of astragali radix on the growth of different cancer cell lines. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2003; 9(4): 670–673.
 64. Lin S, Chang C, Hsu C, Tsai M, Cheng H, Leong MK, et al. Natural compounds as potential adjuvants to cancer therapy: Preclinical evidence. *Br J Pharmacol.* 2020;177(6):1409-1423.
 65. Lin S, Yu C, Hou Y, Huang C, Ho L, Chan S. Transporter-mediated interaction of indican and methotrexate in rats. *J Food Drug Anal.* 2018;26(2S):S133-S140.
 66. Lin S, Yu C, Hou Y, Huang C, Ho L, Chan S. Transporter-mediated interaction of indican and methotrexate in rats. *J Food Drug Anal.* 2018:S133-S140.
 67. Liu J, Liu X, Ma J, Li K, Xu C. The clinical efficacy and safety of kanglaite adjuvant therapy in the treatment of advanced hepatocellular carcinoma: A PRISMA-compliant meta-analysis. *Biosci Rep.* 2019; 39(11): BSR20193319.
 68. Liu L, Fan J, Ai G, Liu J, Luo N, Li C, et al. Berberine in combination with cisplatin induces necroptosis and apoptosis in ovarian cancer cells. *Biol Res.* 2019; 52: 37.
 69. Liu S, Cheng Y. Old formula, new Rx: the journey of PHY906 as cancer adjuvant therapy. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2012;140(3):614-23.
 70. Liu Y, Zhao F, Wang Q, Zhao Q, Hou G, Meng Q. Current Perspectives on Paclitaxel: Focus on

- Its Production, Delivery and Combination Therapy. *Mini Rev Med Chem.* 2023;23:1780-1796.
71. Liu Z, Chen H, Zheng L, Sun L, Shi L. Angiogenic signalling pathways and anti-angiogenic therapy for cancer. *Signal Transduct Target Ther.* 2023;8:198.
 72. Loo WTY, Jin LJ, Chow LWC, Cheung MNB, Wang M. *Rhodiola algida* improves chemotherapy-induced oral mucositis in breast cancer patients. *Expert Opin Investig Drugs.* 2010;19 Suppl1:S91-100.
 73. Lu Y, Liu W, Lv T, Wang Y, Liu T, Chen Y, et al. . Aidi injection reduces doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity by inhibiting carbonyl reductase 1 expression. *Pharm Biol.*2022;60(1):1616–1624.
 74. Lu J, Ye D, Ma B. Constituents, Pharmacokinetics, and Pharmacology of Gegen-Qinlian Decoction. *Front Pharmacol.* 2021;12:668418.
 75. Ma H, Deng Y, Tian Z, Lian Z. Traditional Chinese medicine and immune regulation. *Clin Rev Allergy Immunol.* 2013;44(3):229-41.
 76. Manandhar B, Paudel KR, Sharma B, Karki R. Phytochemical profile and pharmacological activity of *Aegle marmelos* Linn. *J. Integr Med.* 2018;16(3):153-163.
 77. Marconett CN, Morgenstern TJ, Roman AKS, Sundar SN, Singhal AK, Firestone GL. BZL101, a phytochemical extract from the *Scutellaria barbata* plant, disrupts proliferation of human breast and prostate cancer cells through distinct mechanisms dependent on the cancer cell phenotype. *Cancer Biol Ther.* 2010;10(4):397–405.
 78. Martino E, Volpe SD, Terribile E, Benetti E, Sakaj M, Centamore A, et al. The long story of camptothecin: From traditional medicine to drugs. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett.* 2017;27(4):701-707.
 79. Mattioli R, Ilari A, Colotti B, Mosca L, Fazi F, Colotti G. Doxorubicin, and other anthracyclines in cancers: Activity, chemoresistance and its overcoming. *Molecular Aspects of Medicine.* 2023;93.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mam.2023.101205>.
 80. McCulloch M, See C, Shu X, Broffman M, Kramer A, Fan W, et al. Astragalus-based Chinese herbs and platinum-based chemotherapy for advanced non-small-cell lung cancer: meta-analysis of randomized trials. *J Clin Oncol.* 2006;24(3):419-30.
 81. McCulloch M, See C, Shu X-S, Broffman M, Kramer A, Fan W, et al. Astragalus-based Chinese herbs and platinum-based chemotherapy for advanced non-small-cell lung cancer: meta-analysis of randomized trials. *J Clin Oncol.* 2006;24(3):419-30.
 82. Mengwei Ni, Wang H, Wang M, Zhou W, Wu J, Sun B, et al. Comparative Efficacy of Chinese Herbal Injections Combined with Paclitaxel Plus Cisplatin for Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer: A Multidimensional Bayesian Network Meta-Analysis. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.* 2020;2020:1824536.
 83. Min L, Ling W, Hua R, Qi H, Chen S, Wang H, Tang L, Shangguan W. Anti-angiogenic therapy for normalization of tumor vasculature: A potential effect of Buyang Huanwu decoction on nude mice bearing human hepatocellular carcinoma xenografts with high metastatic potential. *Mol Med Rep.* 2016;13(3):2518–2526.
 84. Modarai M, Gertsch J, Suter A, Heinrich M, Kortenkamp A. Cytochrome P450 inhibitory action of Echinacea preparations differs widely and co-varies with alkylamide content. *J Pharm Pharmacol.* 2007;59(4):567-73.
 85. Mrusek M, Seo E, Greten HJ, Simon M, Efferth T. Identification of cellular and molecular factors determining the response of cancer cells to six ergot alkaloids. *Invest New Drugs.* 2015 Feb;33(1):32-44.
 86. Ni B, Song X, Shi B, Wang J, Sun Q, Wang X, Xu M, et al. Research progress of ginseng in the treatment of gastrointestinal cancers. *Front Pharmacol.* 2022;13:1036498.
 87. Nur FNF, Nugraheni N, Salsabila IA, Haryanti S, Da'I M, Meiyanto E. Revealing the Reversal Effect of Galangal (*Alpinia galanga* L.) Extract Against Oxidative Stress in Metastatic Breast Cancer Cells and Normal Fibroblast Cells Intended as a Co- Chemotherapeutic and Anti-Ageing Agent. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev.* 2020; 21(1): 107–117.
 88. Perez AT, Arun B, Tripathy D, Mary A. Tagliaferri, Heather S. Shaw, Gretchen G., et al. A phase 1B dose escalation trial of *Scutellaria barbata* (BZL101) for patients with metastatic

- breast cancer. *Breast Cancer Research and Treatment*. 2010;120:111–118.
89. Phull A, Ahmed M, Park H. Cordyceps militaris as a Bio Functional Food Source: Pharmacological Potential, Anti-Inflammatory Actions and Related Molecular Mechanisms. *Microorganisms*. 2022;10: 405.
 90. Qin T, Zhao X, Yun J, Zhang L, Ruan Z, Pan B. Efficacy, and safety of gemcitabine-oxaliplatin combined with huachansu in patients with advanced gallbladder carcinoma. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2008; 14(33): 5210–5216.
 91. Ratan ZA, Haidere MF, Hong YH, Park SH, Lee J, Lee J, et al. Pharmacological potential of ginseng and its major component ginsenosides. *J Ginseng Res*. 2021;45:199-210.
 92. Safarzadeh E, Shotorbani SS, Baradaran B. Herbal Medicine as Inducers of Apoptosis in Cancer Treatment. *Adv Pharm Bull*. 2014;4:421–427.
 93. Salmerón-Manzano E, Garrido-Cardenas JA, Manzano-Agugliaro F. Worldwide Research Trends on Medicinal Plants. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020;17(10): 3376.
 94. Sari NF, Lestari B, Saputri D, Ahsani AF, Santoso RA, Sasmito E, Meiyanto E. Reveal Cytotoxicity and Antigenotoxicity of Piper nigrum L. Ethanolic Extract and its Combination with Doxorubicin on CHO-K1 Cells. *Indonesian Journal of Cancer Chemoprevention*. 2018, 8(3):110.
 95. Septembre-Malaterre A, Rakoto ML, Marodon C, Bedoui Y, Nakab J, Simon E, et al. Artemisia annua, a Traditional Plant Brought to Light. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2020; 21(14): 4986.
 96. Shankar E, Goel A, Gupta K, Gupta S. Plant flavone apigenin: An emerging anticancer agent. *Curr Pharmacol Rep*. 2017;3:423–446.
 97. Sharifi-Rad J, Rayess YE, Rizk AA, Sadaka C, Zgheib R, Zam W, et al. Turmeric and Its Major Compound Curcumin on Health: Bioactive Effects and Safety Profiles for Food, Pharmaceutical, Biotechnological and Medicinal Applications. *Front Pharmacol*. 2020;11: 01021.
 98. Sharifi-Rad J, Rayess YE, Rizk AA, Sadaka C, Zgheib R, Zam W, et al. Turmeric and Its Major Compound Curcumin on Health: Bioactive Effects and Safety Profiles for Food, Pharmaceutical, Biotechnological and Medicinal Applications. *Front Pharmacol*. 2020;11: 01021.
 99. Sheikhha AFE. Nutritional Profile and Health Benefits of Ganoderma lucidum “Lingzhi, Reishi, or Mannentak” as Functional Foods: Current Scenario and Future Perspectives. *Foods*. 2022; 11(7):1030.
 100. Shweta, Abdullah S, Komal, Kumar A. A brief review on the medicinal uses of Cordyceps militaris. *Pharmacological Research - Modern Chinese Medicine*. 2023;7:00228.
 101. Singh BN, Shankar S, Srivastava RK. Green tea catechin, epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG): mechanisms, perspectives, and clinical applications. *Biochem Pharmacol*. 2011 Dec 15;82:1807-21.
 102. Sohretoglu D, Huang S. Ganoderma lucidum Polysaccharides as an anti-cancer agent. *Anticancer Agents Med Chem*. 2018; 18(5): 667–674.
 103. Sohretoglu D, Shile Huang. Ganoderma lucidum Polysaccharides as an anti-cancer agent. *Anticancer Agents Med Chem*. 2018;18(5): 667–674.
 104. Sohretoglu D, Shile Huang. Ganoderma lucidum Polysaccharides as an anti-cancer agent. *Anticancer Agents Med Chem*. 2018;18: 667–674.
 105. Tafazoli A. Echinacea for Cancer Patients: To Give or Not to Give. *Complement Med Res*. 2020;27(2):112-116.
 106. Tai C, Wang C, Tai C, Lin Y, Lin C, Jian J, et al. Aqueous Extract of Solanum nigrum Leaves Induces Autophagy and Enhances Cytotoxicity of Cisplatin, Doxorubicin, Docetaxel, and 5-Fluorouracil in Human Colorectal Carcinoma Cells. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2013; 2013: 514719.
 107. Tao H, Wu X, Cao J, Peng Y, Wang A, Pei J et al. Rhodiola species: A comprehensive review of traditional use, phytochemistry, pharmacology, toxicity, and clinical study. *Med Res Rev*. 2019;39(5):1779-1850.
 108. Thyagarajan A, Jedinak A, Nguyen H, Terry C, Baldrige LA, Jiang J, et al. Triterpenes from Ganoderma Lucidum induce autophagy in colon cancer through the inhibition of p38 mitogen-activated kinase (p38 MAPK). *Nutr Cancer*. 2010;62:630-40.

109. Tran N, Nguyen M, Le KP, Nguyen N, Tran Q, Le L. Screening of Antibacterial Activity, Antioxidant Activity, and Anticancer Activity of *Euphorbia hirta* Linn. Extracts. *Applied Sciences*. 2020;10:8408; doi:10.3390/app10238408.
110. Tungmunnithum D, Thongboonyou A, Pholboon A, Yangsabai A. Flavonoids and Other Phenolic Compounds from Medicinal Plants for Pharmaceutical and Medical Aspects: An Overview. *Medicines (Basel)*. 2018;5(3):93.
111. Unlu A, Nayir E, Kirca O, Ozdogan M. *Ganoderma Lucidum* (Reishi Mushroom) and cancer. *J BUON*. 2016;21:792-798.
112. Vetvicka V, Vannucci V. Biological properties of andrographolide, an active ingredient of *Andrographis Paniculata*: a narrative review. *Ann Transl Med*. 2021;9:1186.
113. Wang H, Hu H, Rong H, Zhao X. Effects of compound Kushen injection on pathology and angiogenesis of tumor tissues. *Oncol Lett*. 2019; 17(2): 2278–2282.
114. Wang HP, Wang C. Risk undermined in the bilateral pharmaceutical regulatory system in Taiwan. *J Food Drug Anal*. 2018;26: S3–S11.
115. Wang K, Yu Y, Chen H, Chiang Y, Ali M, Shieh T, et al. Recent Advances in *Glycyrrhiza glabra* (Licorice)-Containing Herbs Alleviating Radiotherapy- and Chemotherapy-Induced Adverse Reactions in Cancer Treatment. *Metabolites*. 2022; 12(6): 535.
116. Wang C, Chen C, Wang C, Chang Y, Jian J, Lin C, et al. Cisplatin-, Doxorubicin-, and Docetaxel-Induced Cell Death Promoted by the Aqueous Extract of *Solanum nigrum* in Human Ovarian Carcinoma Cells. *Integr Cancer Ther*. 2015;14(6):546-55.
117. Wang X, Liu Z, Sui X, Qibiao Wu Q, Wang J, Xu C. Elemene injection as adjunctive treatment to platinum-based chemotherapy in patients with stage III/IV non-small cell lung cancer: A meta-analysis following the PRISMA guidelines. *Phytomedicine*. 2019;59:152787.
118. Wei Y, Yang P, Cao S, Zhao L. The combination of curcumin and 5-fluorouracil in cancer therapy. *Arch Pharm Res*. 2018;41(1):1-13.
119. Wen C, Fu L, Huang J, Dai Y, Wang B, Xu G, et al. Curcumin reverses doxorubicin resistance via inhibition the efflux function of ABCB4 in doxorubicin-resistant breast cancer cells. *Mol Med Rep*. 2019; 19(6): 5162–5168.
120. Wen C, Fu L, Huang J, Dai Y, Wang B, Xu G, et al. Curcumin reverses doxorubicin resistance via inhibition the efflux function of ABCB4 in doxorubicin-resistant breast cancer cells. *Mol Med Rep*. 2019;19(6):5162-5168.
121. Wu J, Li Y, He Q, Yang X. Exploration of the Use of Natural Compounds in Combination with Chemotherapy Drugs for Tumor Treatment. *Molecules*. 2023;28(3):1022.
122. Wu X, Yin C, Ma J, Chai S, Zhang C, Yao S, et al. Polyoxypregnanes as safe, potent, and specific ABCB1-inhibitory pro-drugs to overcome multidrug resistance in cancer chemotherapy in vitro and in vivo. *Acta Pharm Sin B*. 2021;11:1885-1902.
123. Xiang Y, Guo Z, Zhu P, Chen J, Huang Y. Traditional Chinese medicine as a cancer treatment: Modern perspectives of ancient but advanced science. *Cancer Med*. 2019;8(5):1958-1975.
124. Xiao Z, Wang C, Zhou M, Hu S, Jiang Y, Huang X, et al. Clinical efficacy, and safety of Aidi injection plus paclitaxel-based chemotherapy for advanced non-small cell lung cancer: A meta-analysis of 31 randomized controlled trials following the PRISMA guidelines. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 2019:228:110-122.
125. Xiao Z, Wang C, Li L, Tang X, Li N, Li J, et al. Clinical Efficacy and Safety of Aidi Injection Plus Docetaxel-Based Chemotherapy in Advanced Nonsmall Cell Lung Cancer: A Meta-Analysis of 36 Randomized Controlled Trials. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2018:2018:7918258.
126. Xiong S, Xiao G. Reverting doxorubicin resistance in colon cancer by targeting a key signaling protein, steroid receptor coactivator. *Exp Ther Med*. 2018; 15(4): 3751–3758.
127. Xu X, Zhu R, Ying R, Zhao M, Wu X, Cao G. Nephrotoxicity of Herbal Medicine and Its Prevention. *Front Pharmacol*. 2020;11: 569551.
128. Xu J, Chen H, Li S. Understanding the Molecular Mechanisms of the Interplay Between Herbal Medicines and Gut Microbiota. *Med Res Rev*. 2017;37(5):1140-1185.

129. Yagüe E, Sun H, Hu Y. East Wind, West Wind: Toward the modernization of traditional Chinese medicine. *Front Neurosci.* 2022;16:1057817.
130. Yang L, He W, Qu H, Jia C, Wang Y, Wang Y, Liu D. Phytochemical Isoliquiritigenin Inhibits Angiogenesis Ex Vivo and Corneal Neovascularization in Mice. *Altern Integr Med* 2014;3:4.
131. Yao K, Ma Y, Ma W, Hu J, Wang C, Chen J, et al. Shenqifuzheng injection combined with chemotherapy in the treatment of advanced gastric cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Cancer Res Ther.* 2014;10 Suppl 1:70-4.
132. Yeh M, Wu H, Lin N, Hsieh J, Yeh J, Chiu H, et al. Long-term use of combined conventional medicine and Chinese herbal medicine decreases the mortality risk of patients with lung cancer. *Complement Ther Med.* 2020;52:102427.
133. Yin OQP, Gallagher N, Li A, Zhou W, Harrell R, Schran H. Effect of grapefruit juice on the pharmacokinetics of nilotinib in healthy participants. *J Clin Pharmacol.* 2010;50(2):188-94.
134. Yu J, Wang J, Yang J, Ouyang T, Gao H, Kan H, et al. New insight into the mechanisms of Ginkgo biloba leaves in the treatment of cancer. *Phytomedicine.* 2024;122:155088.
135. Yu YK, Son D, Chung TH, Yong-Jae Lee YJ. A Review of the Pharmacological Efficacy and Safety of Licorice Root from Corroborative Clinical Trial Findings. *J Med Food.* 2020;23(1):12-20.
136. Zhang D, Wu J, Liu S, Zhang X, Zhang B. Network meta-analysis of Chinese herbal injections combined with the chemotherapy for the treatment of pancreatic cancer. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2017;96(21):e7005.
137. Zhang F, Zhang T, Jiang T, Zhang R, Teng Z, Li C, et al. Wortmannin potentiates roscovitine-induced growth inhibition in human solid tumor cells by repressing PI3K/Akt pathway. *Cancer Lett.* 2009;286(2):232-9.
138. Zhang T, Shi T, Li Y, Mu W, Zhang H, Yang Li, et al. Polysaccharides extracted from *Rheum tanguticum* ameliorate radiation-induced enteritis via activation of Nrf2/HO-1. *J Radiat Res.* 2021;62(1):46-57.
139. Zhang W, Zhao Y, Bai X, Hui G, Lombardi JR, Zhao D, et al. The auxiliary determination of the binding site of berberine binding to human serum albumin by surface-enhanced Raman scattering. *Vibrational Spectroscopy.* 2011;55:65-68.
140. Zhao H, Han Z, Li G, Zhang S, Luo Y. Therapeutic Potential and Cellular Mechanisms of *Panax Notoginseng* on Prevention of Aging and Cell Senescence-Associated Diseases. *Aging Dis.* 2017;8(6):721-739.
141. Zhao L, Zhao H, Zhao Y, Sui M, Liu J, Li P, et al. Role of Ginseng, Quercetin, and Tea in Enhancing Chemotherapeutic Efficacy of Colorectal Cancer. *Front Med (Lausanne).* 2022;9: 939424.
142. Zhao M, Ma J, Li M, Zhang Y, Jiang B, Zhao X, et al. Cytochrome P450 Enzymes and Drug Metabolism in Humans. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2021; 22(23):12808.
143. Zhao M, Ma J, Li M, Zhang Y, Jiang B, Zhao X, Huai C, et al. Cytochrome P450 Enzymes and Drug Metabolism in Humans. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2021;22:12808.
144. Zhao M, Ma J, Li M, Zhang Y, Jiang B, Zhao X, et al. Cytochrome P450 Enzymes and Drug Metabolism in Humans. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2021;22(23):12808.
145. Zhao D, Long X, Chen J, Wang J. Aidi injection combined with chemotherapy in the treatment of cancer patients: a systematic review of systematic reviews and meta-analyses. *Anticancer Drugs.* 2021;32(10):991-1002

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